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Date

GRADUATE SCHOOL

ON GAS/AIR POROSITY
IN PRESSURE DIE CASTING

A THESIS
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Genick Bar-Meir

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Abstract

Multifunctional characteristics of die casting parts are significantly compromised by the presence of voids; a substantial decrease in the elastic moduli and thermal conductivity results. Gas/air inclusions constitutes a large part of the total porosity. To reduce the porosity due to gas/air entrainment, several methods can be applied to remove the residual air in the die. In some cases these methods yield good results, i.e. low porosity, while in other cases the results are not satisfactory. The purpose of this work is to analyze the main mechanisms that control gas/air porosity and to examine the mixing process in the die cavity.

Analyses of vacuum and atmospheric venting indicate that there is a critical vent area below which the ventilation is poor and above which the resistance to the air flow is minimal. Models yield simple equations to calculate the required area which is a function of the duct resistance, the evacuated volume, and the filling time. These results should be useful to the design engineer and for numerical simulations of the cavity filling which takes into account the compressibility of the gas flow out.

In the Pore Free Technique, oxygen is introduced into the die to react with the liquid metal. The vacuum created by the reaction reduces the porosity. Differing results obtained with this method can be explained by a model based on the conservation laws. The model indicates that there is a critical dimensionless parameter which describes the border between successful and unsuccessful operation.

The liquid metal enters the die cavity in many designs as a wall jet. Experiments demonstrate that the jet has at least two main flow patterns: continuous flow and spray flow. High speed photography was used to obtain qualitative and quantitative information on the jet flow.

ב"ה

העבודה הזאת מוקדשת לשירלי אישתי
זכרתי את לכתך אחרי בדרך לא דרך במדבר ציה

This work is dedicated to Shirley

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Nomenclature

A	vent or gate cross sectional area, [m^2]
A_c	critical vent cross sectional area which makes $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$, [m^2]
A_{c1}	critical vent cross sectional area which makes $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$ based on die volume, [m^2]
A_{c2}	critical gate cross sectional area which makes $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$ based on cylinder volume. [m^2]
A_F	liquid metal "fresh" area, [m^2]
C	oxygen molar concentration, [$moles/m^3$]
C_{bulk}	oxygen molar concentration at gas bulk, [$moles/m^3$]
C^*	oxygen molar concentration at liquid metal bulk, [$moles/m^3$]
D	duct hydraulic diameter, [m]
D_G	oxygen molecular diffusion coefficient into nitrogen, [m/sec^2]
D_L	oxygen molecular diffusion coefficient into liquid metal, [m/sec^2]
K_G	mass transfer coefficient of oxygen in the gas phase, [m/sec]
K_L	mass transfer coefficient of oxygen in liquid phase, [m/sec]
K_t	total oxygen mass transfer coefficient to liquid metal, [m/sec]
L	length or equivalent length of the vent or runner, [m]
L_{max}	maximum length of vent or runner in which flow is not choked, [m]
$\overline{M}$	Mach numbers ratio, equation (4.14)
M_{exit}	Mach number at duct exit
M_{in}	Mach number at duct entrance
M_{max}	maximum possible Mach number at duct entrance

M_{O_2}	oxygen molecular weight, $[kg/kgmole]$
M_{N_2}	nitrogen molecular weight, $[kg/kgmole]$
P	gas ¹ pressure at the cylinder or chamber, $[kPa]$
P_{atm}	atmospheric pressure, $[kPa]$
$\bar{P}$	pressure ratio. equation (3.13) and equation (6.12)
P_{exit}	pressure at duct exit, $[kPa]$
P_0	total or stagnation pressure, $[kPa]$
P_{O_2}	partial pressure of oxygen in the cylinder, $[kPa]$
P_{vacuum}	lowest pressure in vacuum tank, $[kPa]$
R	universal gas constant, $8.314 kJ/Kgmol/K$
T	air temperature at cylinder or chamber. $[K]$
T_0	total or stagnation temperature. $[K]$
V	cylinder volume or the chamber volume, $[m^3]$
V_e	bulge velocity in the jet direction (see Figure 7.8), $[m/sec]$
V_n	bulge velocity perpendicular to the jet direction (see Figure 7.8), $[m/sec]$
V_{tank}	vacuum tank volume, $[m^3]$
c	speed of sound, $[m/sec]$
f	friction factor
k	ratio of specific heats. $\frac{c_p}{c_v}$,
k_1	reaction constant (for pseudo first-order chemical reaction), $[sec^{-1}]$
m	air mass in cylinder or chamber. $[kg]$
$\bar{m}$	fraction of air mass in cylinder. equation (3.20)
$\dot{m}_{in}$	air mass flow rate into duct or out of cylinder, $[kg/sec]$
$\dot{m}_{in}^*$	approximate air mass flow rate into duct when flow is first choked and pressure and temperature remain in their initial state. $[kg/sec]$, equation (4.13).
$\bar{n}$	fraction of moles of oxygen (air) in cylinder, equation (6.18)
n_{O_2}	moles of oxygen in the cylinder, $[moles]$
$\dot{n}_{O_2out}$	oxygen molar flux due to reaction, $[m/sec]$
t	time measured from blockage of pouring hole to time when liquid metal

	first reaches the gate/vent ² , $0 \leq t \leq t_{max}$, [sec]
t^*	reaction time, time for the reaction to practically finished, [sec]
$\bar{t}$	dimensionless time, also fraction of cylinder volume, equation (3.16)
t_c	characteristic time to evacuate cylinder or chamber, [sec], equation (3.12)
t_{cR}	characteristic time to deplete oxygen in the cylinder, [sec]. equation (6.11)
t_{max}	filling time. the time for liquid metal to reach the vent, [sec]
t_{maxC}	cylinder filling time, the time for liquid metal to reach the gate, [sec]
v	specific volume, [m^3/kg], equation (3.6)
(0)	signifies air initial state in the cylinder or chamber
(t)	signifies any time during filling of the cylinder or chamber

Subscripts

i	indicates both the cylinder and the chamber
1	indicates the cylinder
2	indicates the chamber

Greek symbol

σ	collision diameter of air molecule, 3.5 [$\text{\AA}$]
----------	--

¹ P denotes the partial pressure of the oxygen for the Pore Free Technique model

²this time starts from the same point in Chapters 3-5, while in the Pore Free Technique model time is measured from the moment the piston moves

Chapter 1

DIE CASTING PROCESS

The casting process is one of the oldest metal technologies. In this technology metal in the liquid phase is poured into a prepared mold to be solidified and to obtain its form. After the solidification the mold is removed. This process is somewhat slow. The mold has to be rebuilt for every run and the actual casting process takes time.

To overcome these drawbacks the liquid metal is forced into permanent mold; this is called pressure die casting. An example of this transition is a die casting machine from the turn of century (1905) as shown in Figure 1.1. In this machine the shot sleeve is immersed inside the liquid metal bath. The metal enters the shot sleeve from a hole below. After the plunger moves for a short distance the hole is covered and liquid metal is pushed upwards. The die halves are closed and turned on the top of the shot sleeve before the movement of the plunger. The liquid metal enters the die and is solidified. The die is turned into its vertical position and the cast is pulled out. This machine was operated by a crew of three strong men or more.

The cast, in this case, has smoother surfaces than in other casting processes with more details. Additionally, to accelerate the process a cooling system is used in later die casting machines. These fast processes of filling and cooling cause a problem in an evacuation of the air and other gases from the die. This problem is magnified when the other requirements are applied. To minimize the secondary machining such as trimming,

Figure 1.1: A schematic of Doehler's first die casting machine

the gates and vents have to be very narrow. A typical size of the vent and gate thickness is in the range of 1 to 2mm.

In modern cold chamber die casting machine shown in Figure 1.2, the liquid metal flows into the shot sleeve from a hole, referred to herein as the pouring hole. The shot sleeve is filled to a certain level and then the plunger pushes the liquid metal into the mold cavity. Some of the liquid metal is solidified on the surface of the shot sleeve. Only the metal in the liquid form enters into the cavity. The solidified liquid metal is scraped by the plunger and remains at the "end of the stroke". This is sometime referred to as the biscuit. This biscuit and the cast with the vent and runner system are removed in the end of the run. Then the mold and plunger are sprayed with lubricant and the cycle repeats itself.

In regular casting the vent is connected to the atmosphere; this is referred to herein as air venting. In extreme cases when air venting does not produce good results, there is a need to take additional steps. This happens for a very complicated cavity shape where air is entrapped in some sections of the cavity that are blocked. Solutions devised to date are: evacuating the cavities, Pore Free (in zinc and aluminum casting) and Squeeze Casting. Squeeze Casting is used to obtain a spray free filling process in which air will hopefully

not penetrate the metal surface. Pore Free and Vacuum Venting Techniques are used to minimize the amount of the residual air mass before it is entrained.

Figure 1.2: A schematic of modern horizontal die casting machine

Pressure die casting machines are generally divided into two categories; the cold chamber and hot chamber. The hot chamber machine is a machine in which the cylinder is heated while in the cold chamber it is not. The models described in this thesis are applicable to both types of machines. The filling time in a cold chamber is shorter to prevent freezing. The porosity problem is augmented with the smaller filling time. Thus, the problem is typical for the cold chamber; the term cold chamber is used here. The reader can interpret the "cold" chamber as "hot" chamber. Die casting machines are also divided into two different categories: horizontal and vertical shot sleeve. The horizontal machines required less power to push the liquid metal through the gate and runner. Hence, the possible injection time can be achieved on smaller machine (see Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3: A schematic of "hot" and "cold" die casting machines

Chapter 2

INTRODUCTION

2.1 General Remarks

Porosity from entrapped gas is a major production problem in many die casting products. Porosity results in degradation of both the moduli of elasticity and thermal conductivity. The quality of products can be improved only when the chief sources of the porosity are minimized. In order for them to be minimized, the sources have to be categorized properly and solutions to the major sources have to be found.

2.2 The Aims and The Scope of This Work

Porosity can be divided into two main categories: shrinkage porosity and gas/air entrainment. This work focuses on the gas/air entrainment. The creation of gas/air entrainment can be attributed to at least four categories: lubricant evaporation (and reaction processes¹), vent locations (last place to be filled), mixing processes, and vent/gate area. The effects of lubricant evaporation have to been found to be insignificant, and those of vent location can be considered solved. Some mixing processes have been investigated and can be considered solved. The other mixing processes are studied here. Insufficient vent/gate area causes significant porosity. The objectives of the present analyses are to

¹Some researchers view the chemical reactions (e.g. release of nitrogen during solidification process) as category by itself. In this study the chemical reactions are taken to be part of the gas/air entrainment.

build models which include the main mechanisms in vent/gate area and to study the other mixing processes. The results are presented in an easy-to-use form and at along with the affecting parameters.

2.3 Background

In this section the four categories affecting porosity are discussed and solutions for some causes are presented.

2.3.1 Lubricant evaporation and chemical reaction

Lewis et al (1961) and Lindsey and Wallace (1972) have shown that lubricant evaporation does not play an important role in the porosity formation. The difference in the gas solubility (mostly hydrogen) of liquid and solid can be shown to be insignificant (ASM 1987). For example, the maximum hydrogen release due to phase change of a kilogram of aluminum is about 7cm^3 at standard condition (atmospheric). This amount is less than 3% of the volume needed to be displaced and therefore can be neglected.

On the other hand the most significant reaction occurs between the oxygen and the liquid metal. In this reaction, oxygen is depleted and the gas mass to be evacuated is reduced. This reaction is not instantaneous; it requires time due to resistance to mass transfer in the gas phase. Only part of the oxygen is depleted. The magnitude of this part depends on a dimensionless parameter which represents the relationship between the rate of reaction and the resistance to oxygen flow to the interface. The oxygen in the initial stages of the stroke remains practically unchanged, and only in the later stages does the percentage change. Hence, it can be assumed that these reactions (oxidation and hydrogne reease) are canceling each other. This topic is discussed in Chapter 6 of this thesis. No significant volume change has been reported in the literature due to lubricant evaporation and chemical reaction.

2.3.2 Vent location or last place to be filled

Earlier studies on the location of the last place to be filled were approached by experimental methods (Peikert 1964; Varaprasatham 1966). Since computers have become more powerful, the approach has changed and numerical simulations have been used, for example, Minaie et al (1991) and Hu et al (1992). Numerical simulations based on an array of methods including finite element, finite volume and finite difference yield reasonably good results. Commercial codes are also available in the market. These numerical codes require a long run time. The exponential rate of growth of the computer power makes this drawback temporary and it is anticipated that in the future this problem will disappear.

2.3.3 Mixing processes

The mixing processes can be divided according to the location where they occur; the shot sleeve and the die cavity. Garber (1982) has shown the existence of a critical velocity above and below which air entrapment occurs. Koch (1974), Bühler (1974), Young and Brisssing (1993) and others suggested using an accelerated injection velocity (parabolic profile) to suppress the formation of a wave. Lewis et al (1989) and Vonn (1993) investigated experimentally the velocity function and showed that the velocity function indeed influences the wave formation. The implementation to the real operation of a die casting process appears partially successful.

While there is disagreement in the literature concerning what the desirable liquid metal minimum gate velocity is, all the researchers agree that the liquid metal velocity has a minimum value to achieve spray flow. The existence of a minimum velocity hints that a significant change in the liquid metal flow pattern occurs. Liquid metal flow patterns can be divided into three main regions: continuous flow jet, coarse particle jet, and an atomized particle jet (Maier 1974). Some researchers recommended that atomized jet should be used for complex configurations and thin sections (Belopukhov

and Korotkov 1969). Some researchers used water analogy to study flow inside the cavity for example, (Stuhrke and Wallace 1966). New contributions to the understanding of the mixing processes will be presented in Chapter 7 of this thesis.

2.3.4 Vent/gate area

Decrease of porosity level with increase of vent area was reported by Draper (1967) and Luis and Draper (1967) for atmospheric venting. Moreover, Draper (1967) found that porosity decreased with increasing vent area or filling time until the vent area or filling time reached or exceeded a critical value, after which the porosity remains constant. Lindsey and Wallace (1972) have shown that the porosity decreases with decrease of the evacuated volume. These important findings demonstrate that the critical vent area is crucial to the reduction of porosity. Unfortunately, the shape, geometry and other technical information of the venting system and other parts were not reported; thus the resistance in the venting system in these experiments cannot be calculated. Only qualitative comparisons can be made.

Previous studies on the relation between vent and gate area came to contradictory conclusions. The gate area is larger than the vent area in typical designs. Some recommend the gate area be twice the vent area (Barton 1962; Rearwin 1960). Draper (1967) found experimentally no relation between the gate and vent areas and porosity. Luis and Draper (1967) have shown that there is an optimum gate area. The combined resistances of the vent and gate have to adequately satisfy certain constraints has been found experimentally (Peikert 1964; Varaprasatham 1966). Clearly, the restrictions on both the vent area and the gate area have to be addressed.

2.4 Closely Related Work

In this section, the analytical models for the vent area for different modes of operation are described. The most widely used method is to operate the die casting when the vent is opened to the atmosphere. This method is referred herein as air venting, and it is useful when the mixing processes are not significant. In some designs, air venting yields good results, while in others the results are not satisfactory. The following models try to explain this inconstancy.

Sachs (1952) developed a model based on the following assumptions: 1) the gas undergoes an isentropic process in the die cavity, 2) a quasi steady state exists, 3) the only resistance to the gas flow is in the vent entrance, 4) a maximum mass flow rate is present, and 5) the liquid metal has no surface tension, thus the metal pressure is equal to the gas pressure. Sachs also differentiated between two cases: choked flow and un-choked flow (but this differentiation did not come into play in his model). Assumption 3 requires that for choked flow the pressure ratio be about two between the cavity and vent exit.

Veinik (1962) independently developed a similar model. He assumed that the flow is choked instantaneously and argues that because the flow is choked the lowest pressure in the cavity is equal to about two atmospheres (similar to assumptions (3) and (4) of Sachs). Based on this postulation, the vent area can be calculated. Veinik, in a latter paper, (1966) introduced a factor to account for the friction in the venting system but the pressure is still assumed to be two atmospheres. Lindsey and Wallace (1972) looked at values of the variables in Veinik's equation and argued for different values. Draper and Peikert (1967) derived a similar equation independently.

All these models neglect the friction in the venting system with the exception of Veinik (1966). The vent design in a commercial systems includes at least an exit, several ducts, and several abrupt expansions/contractions in which the resistance coefficient can

be evaluated to be larger than $\frac{4fL}{D} = 3$ and a typical value of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ is about 7 or more ($\frac{4fL}{D}$ is a measure of the resistance). It will be shown² in Chapter (3) in this case that the pressure ratio for the choking condition is at least 3 and the pressure ratio reaches this value only after about 2/3 of the piston stroke is elapsed. Furthermore, as will be shown in Chapter 4, when the flow is choked the pressure in the cavity does not remain constant as assumed in the models but increases exponentially.

In the presentation of Sachs (1952) and Draper (1967), the air velocity at the vent is tied to the liquid metal velocity at the gate, while Veinik presents the calculation of the vent area as a ratio of the air volume to the air velocity. Transformation of the results presented in Veinik's form to the one adapted by Sachs (1952) and Draper (1967) requires the volume flow rate at the gate and vent entrance to be equal. This transformation also requires that pressure on both sides of the liquid metal to be equal. The pressure difference on both sides of the liquid metal interface depends on the surface tension and on the curvature which is an unknown function of time. Likewise, the ratio of the gate volume flow rate to the vent entrance volume flow rate depends on the resistance in the runner and the vent systems. Experiments carried out by Varaprasatham (1966) have showed differences between of the values based on these models and the experimental values.

Bennett (1990) has proposed another model to calculate the vent area for a cavity evacuated to the atmosphere. In this model, the vent area is calculated based on the assumption that the pressure in the cavity remains constant during the filling time and the flow is not choked. Consequently, the air volume flow rate at the vent is equal to the liquid metal flow rate at the gate. The vent area and the pressure are determined from the flow through an orifice. The Sachs (1952), Draper (1967), Veinik (1962) and Lindsey and Wallace (1972) models stay on one side of extreme (i. e. always choked flow), while

²see Figure 3.6

the Bennett model stays on the other extreme (i. e. not choked at all).

Karni (1991) proposed a model to describe the pressure variations in the cavity for atmospheric venting attempting to take into account the resistance in the venting system. In the outlined procedure, the calculation of the pressure for the choked condition in the cavity is related to the ambient pressure and temperature. These calculations are correct where the flow is un-choked³. However, when the flow is choked, the flow at the venting system entrance is not affected by the atmospheric condition (exit condition).

When the flow is un-choked, the vent entrance Mach number to the venting system is assumed and then is used to calculate the exit Mach number. These Mach numbers enable one to calculate the pressure and temperature at the entrance to the venting system based on the pressure outside the vent. In these calculations the assumption about the entrance Mach number has not been checked to see whether if it consistent with the results. Additionally, the temperature in the cavity for Karni's model is assumed to be constant. This assumption significantly affects the pressure in the cavity for this model. It makes this model simpler but is in disagreement with reality.

2.5 Overview of This Thesis

The thesis contains eight Chapters. Chapter 1 starts with the general introduction to the die casting process. This chapter describes why pressure die casting started and the operation of the die casting process.

Chapter 2 covers the introduction and provides the general background overview of the porosity problem in die casting. It addresses the need for analytical investigation of air flow out of the cavity. The objectives of the present investigation in terms of analyzing and presenting results is also described.

³The other possible condition is when the pressures on both sides of the vent are matched and the exit conditions are indeed the ambient.

Chapter 3 presents an analytical model of vacuum venting. It describes the parameters which affect the process. The working parameters, due to the simplicity of the solution, are discussed. It also illustrates how to apply this method to real cases.

Chapter 4 discusses the case of atmospheric venting. It also presents two methods of solving the Mach numbers: first, general numerical approach, and second, analytical method for the limiting case for small Mach numbers. The importance of the area ratio, $\frac{A}{A_C}$, and how $\frac{4fL}{D}$ is included in $\frac{A}{A_C}$ is pointed out. The implementation of this solution in the industry is suggested.

Chapter 5 describes the model for the pressure variation in two chambers. It determines the requirements on the gate area. It also provides a tool to examine the error in the models of the previous two chapters created by taking the air as combining the cold chamber with the die cavity. It also provides the relationship between the gate area and the resistance in the runner.

Chapter 6 describes a model for the Pore Free Technique. It provides a general rule as to when Pore Free technique is the better choice and when the vacuum venting is the better choice. It also provides guidelines for improving the operational performance. This model can be used to examine the gas volume in the previous three chapters.

Chapter 7 describes the experimental study undertaken in this thesis. A mechanism for possible air entrapment is shown. The experimental technique is also described.

Finally, Chapter 8 describes the conclusions of the present study. The limitations of this work are discussed and recommendations for future extensions of the present investigation are also given.

Chapter 3

VACUUM VENTING

3.1 Introduction

The idea that vacuum venting can be applied to the process of die casting is almost as old as the die casting process itself. The first American patent on vacuum pumping was in 1915 by C. M. Grey. Brunner and Trebes patented a second process in 1941. Significant commercial use started during the late 1950's and early 1960's pushed by the developments of the cold chamber machine. During these years, other companies also developed patents; for example, Ube in Japan, and Hodler in Europe. In a cold chamber machine, the filling time is shorter due to lack of heating. In this case, the liquid metal velocity is higher and the amount of the mixing is increased. A vacuum is applied to remove the residual gases before they have the possibility of mixing.

This method has additional benefits besides the reduction of the porosity. The pressure on the die is reduced and therefore, the life span of the mold is extended. With vacuum venting, it is possible to produce parts which were not possible to produce conventionally. Thus, the usage of vacuum venting compared to conventional venting increases the scope of products which could be manufactured by this technology. Discussion on the methods that vacuum are applied can be found in Kaye (1982).

Mathematically, vacuum venting is a special case of atmospheric venting. Due to

its special mode of operation and the simplicity of the analysis, the vacuum venting is examined in this Chapter. This simple analysis allows one to learn the effects of the operating parameters and to extrapolate them to other modes of operation. From a construction/operation point of view, the vacuum venting is more complicated. It requires a vacuum pump, and vacuum tank and the operator has to clean the lubricant filter. The porosity in this model of operation is less than that obtained in atmospheric venting, but it is 10% to 15% more expensive.

One of the differences between vacuum venting and atmospheric venting occurs in the start up time. For vacuum venting, a choking condition is established almost instantaneously (it depends on the air volume in the venting duct), while in the atmospheric case the volume of the air has to be reduced to more than half before a choking condition develops. Moreover, the flow is not necessarily choked in atmospheric venting as it will be revealed in the next Chapter. Once the flow is choked, there is no difference in calculating the flow for the two cases.

Extensive research has been conducted on vacuumizing a space. Traditionally, it has been assumed that the time to evacuate a cavity by a vacuum pump is very large and the volume flow rate at the vent is constant or a known function of time. Most books on vacuum technology, for example Roth (1953), contain solutions for this type of problem. In die casting, however, the process occurs over a very short period of time (typically times of 10 to 50 milliseconds). A design calculation shows that a large and expensive pump would be required to maintain the vacuum over the injection period. On the other hand, there is a long period of time between injections in which there is no need to apply a vacuum. This non-continuous demand suggests a system in which the pump is not directly connected to the cavity, but rather to a large vacuum tank which is connected to the die cavity. This arrangement enables efficient use of the pump power and, therefore, a smaller pump is needed. The vacuum tank is maintained at almost constant pressure

during the process. Discussion on the size of the tank to maintain this requirement is given in Appendix A.

Figure 3.1: A schematic of an actual vacuum venting in pressure die casting arrangement

3.2 The Model

In Figure 3.1 a schematic of a commercial die casting system with a vacuum tank is shown. In order to better understand the process, the following model is proposed. The cold chamber (unfilled volume of the shot sleeve) and the die cavity with the runner are combined and called the cylinder. This may be done because of their relatively small resistance to the air flow compared with the resistance to the flow in the venting system (see in Chapter 5 for more details). A piston moving with a known velocity pushes the liquid metal and both of them propel the air through a long duct. In reality, there is not a long duct but a "zig-zag" duct which can be represented by an equivalent long straight duct (Jeppson 1976). The liquid metal can be considered part of the piston (see Figure 3.2). For the duration of the process considered here the velocity of the piston is assumed to be constant. In the actual process, the velocity is not constant but increases in a step

Figure 3.2: A simplified model for vacuum venting

Figure 3.3: A typical piston velocity diagram after Kaye, A. and Street, A. (1982)

change at the end of the piston stroke. Yet, during most of the piston stroke ($\approx 95\%$ or more) the speed is almost constant (see Figure 3.3). The initial velocity causes less air entrainment and the final increased velocity reduces the volume of the air which is already entrapped by increasing the pressure.

The equation that describes the volume of air in the cylinder cavity during the time when the piston moves can be written in the following form:

$$V(t) = V(0) \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{max}}\right) \quad (3.1)$$

where

t time counted from the start of the vacuum to end of process. $0 \leq t \leq t_{max}$,

t_{max} filling time, the time for the liquid metal to reach the vent, and
 $V(0)$ initial volume of air in the cylinder cavity.

t_{max} is primarily a function of the solidification process. Some correlations can yield an approximate value for t_{max} . For example, Allsop and Kennedy (1983) recommend for aluminum $t_{max}[ms] = 40 \times average\ thickness[mm]$. The air mass at any particular time in the cylinder cavity is given by the ideal gas relation:

$$m(t) = \frac{P(t)V(t)}{RT(t)}. \quad (3.2)$$

The pressure in the cylinder is assumed to be uniform. The air in the cylinder undergoes a free expansion or compression process. It is shown in Appendix B that the process is isentropic under the assumptions that this model was constructed. Even when the assumptions are not valid the isentropic relationship can be assumed for low piston Mach number, low turbulence level and negligible heat transfer (Annand and Roe 1974). Hence, the relationship between the pressure and the temperature in the cylinder and chamber is

$$\frac{T(t)}{T(0)} = \left[\frac{P(t)}{P(0)} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}}. \quad (3.3)$$

A simplified form substituting equation (3.3) into equation (3.2) yields

$$m(t) = \frac{P(0)V(t)}{RT(0)} \left[\frac{P(t)}{P(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}}. \quad (3.4)$$

Differentiation of equation (3.4) with respect to time yields

$$\frac{dm(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{v(0)} \left[\frac{P(t)}{P(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{1}{k} \frac{V(t)}{P(t)} \frac{dP(t)}{dt} + \frac{dV(t)}{dt} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

where:

$$v(0) = \frac{RT(0)}{P(0)}. \quad (3.6)$$

Note that in the cylinder $P \approx P_0$ and $T \approx T_0$, where the subscript 0 indicates total or stagnation values.

The flow in the duct can be approximated as Fanno flow (adiabatic flow). The reason for this approximation is that the duration of the process is short and as such the heat transfer is negligible. The flow is choked when the pressure ratio between the vacuum tank and the cylinder cavity is less than the critical value of 0.52828, or a lower critical value depending on the pressure drop in the venting duct. For this kind of flow one can use the well known equation (Shapiro 1953, pages 159–189)

$$\frac{4fL}{D} = \frac{1 - M_{in}^2}{kM_{in}^2} + \frac{k+1}{2k} \ln \left[\frac{(k+1)M_{in}^2}{2 \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{in}^2\right)} \right]. \quad (3.7)$$

Equation (3.7) shows that the Mach number at the entrance to the duct, M_{in} , for choked flow, is independent of the pressure and temperature and depends only on the resistance in the duct. For the given geometrical parameters of the duct, the Mach number can be easily calculated (Shapiro 1953, pages 159–189). Equation (3.7) is also independent of the pressure in the vacuum tank as long as the pressure ratio exceeds the critical value. Further discussion about the size of the tank in order to maintain this condition is given in Appendix A.

The mass flow rate of air into the tank can be written (Shapiro 1953, pages 84–85)

$$\dot{m}_{in} = AP(t)M_{in} \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT(t)}} \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{in}^2 \right]^{\frac{-(k+1)}{2(k-1)}}. \quad (3.8)$$

This equation indicates that the mass flow rate depends on the stagnation pressure and stagnation temperature in the cylinder and varies during the injection period. Yet, it must be kept in mind that the pressure in the vacuum tank does not have any effect on the mass flow rate after it reached choked conditions. Since the temperature is a function of the pressure (equation (3.3)), the mass flow rate of air can be expressed with only one

independent variable.

$$\dot{m}_{in} = AM_{in}P(0) \left(\frac{P(t)}{P(0)} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT(0)}} \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{in}^2 \right]^{\frac{-(k+1)}{2(k-1)}}. \quad (3.9)$$

The mass balance of the air in the cylinder cavity is

$$\frac{dm(t)}{dt} + \dot{m}_{in} = 0. \quad (3.10)$$

3.3 Solution

Substituting equation (3.5) and (3.9) into (3.10) yields

$$\left[\bar{P} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{1}{k} \frac{V(t)}{\bar{P}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dt} + \frac{dV}{dt} \right\} + \frac{V(0)}{t_c} \left[\bar{P} \right]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} = 0 \quad (3.11)$$

where:

$$t_c = \frac{m(0)}{\dot{m}_{in}(0)} = \frac{m(0)}{AM_{in}P(0) \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT(0)}} \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{in}^2 \right]^{\frac{-(k+1)}{2(k-1)}}}, \quad (3.12)$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{P(t)}{P(0)}, \quad (3.13)$$

$m(0)$ is the initial mass of the air in the cylinder and $\dot{m}_{in}(0)$ is its initial mass flow rate. The parameter t_c represents the time which it would takes to evacuate the cylinder when the mass flow rate remains constant during the filling process.

Note that $\frac{dV}{dt}$ according equation (3.1) is equal to $-\frac{V(0)}{t_{max}}$ and equation (3.11) can be written as

$$\frac{V(0)}{\bar{P}} \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{max}} \right) \frac{d\bar{P}}{dt} - k \frac{V(0)}{t_{max}} + k \frac{V(0)}{t_c} \left[\bar{P} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

Equation (3.14) is an ordinary differential equation which can be rearranged to obtain the form

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{dt} = \frac{k \left(\frac{1}{t_{max}} - \frac{1}{t_c} \bar{P}^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} \right)}{1 - \frac{t}{t_{max}}} \bar{P}. \quad (3.15)$$

A dimensionless time can be defined as

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{t_{max}}. \quad (3.16)$$

The dimensionless time also can be interpreted as a fraction of the volume of the cylinder.

Substituting equation (3.16) into (3.15) yields

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{d\bar{t}} = \frac{k \left(1 - \frac{t_{max}}{t_c} \bar{P}^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} \right)}{1 - \bar{t}} \bar{P}. \quad (3.17)$$

Equation (3.17) can be solved analytically in an infinite series, however, there is an advantage in solving it numerically and presenting the results graphically. In case of zero vent area, no air mass is leaving the cylinder and equation (3.17) can be solved to obtain the solution

$$\bar{P} = (1 - \bar{t})^{-k}. \quad (3.18)$$

The fraction of the air mass left in the cavity as a function of time can be determined by using (3.1), (3.2) and (3.3)

$$\bar{m} = \bar{P}^{\frac{1}{k}} (1 - \bar{t}), \quad (3.19)$$

where:

$$\bar{m} = \frac{m(t)}{m(0)}. \quad (3.20)$$

3.4 Results and Discussion

The results of this model are presented in figures 3.4 through 3.8. In Figure 3.4 the pressure ratio, $\bar{P}$, is presented as a function of the dimensionless time (the piston stroke). The mass fraction as a function of the time is exhibited in figure 3.5. Figure 3.6 describes the Mach number and the critical pressure ratio as a function of the $\frac{A}{D}$. In Figure 3.7 the pressure ratio when 0.9 of the piston stroke is elapsed, $\bar{P}(\bar{t} = 0.9)$, describes as a

function of the area ratio, $\frac{A}{A_C}$. The area ratio, $\frac{A}{A_C}$, is described as function of the mass fraction when 0.9 of the piston stroke is elapsed.

Before getting into a discussion of the results it is interesting to point out the importance of the time ratio $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$. This parameter represents the ratio between the filling time which is determined by the solidification process and the time which would be required to evacuate the cavity if the pressure and temperature in the cavity would remain constant. This ratio also represents the relationship between two effects, the "vacuumizing flow rate" which reduces the pressure and piston compression rate which increases the pressure. When the ratio is equal to unity, the pressure in the cylinder and the mass flow rate are constant. This is the breakeven point: if $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$ is greater than one the pressure will decrease and if $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$ is less than one the pressure will increase as shown in Figure 4, which was obtained by an integration of equation (3.17).

Equation (3.12) illustrates that t_c is decreased when the vent area and/or the Mach number are increased. Therefore, increasing the vent area and/or the Mach number increases the time ratio, $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$. The Mach number is a function of the resistance in the venting system. The highest value the Mach number can obtained is one which the limiting case of the models discussed in the introduction. This is the case where no resistance in the venting system present. Hence, reducing the flow resistance of the venting system has limited effect on the pressure in the cylinder. The resistance which makes the time ratio equal to one is the critical resistance and has the corresponding critical Mach number. The limitation on the size of the vent area is geometrical and determined by how large the vent area can be. The critical vent area is the one which makes the time ratio equal to one. As long as the vent area is larger than the critical area, or in other words the resistance in the venting system is less than the critical one, the pressure in the cylinder will decrease.

The critical area is the area which makes the time ratio, $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$. Thus the time ratio, $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$, can be expressed by the area ratio, $\frac{A}{A_c}$. The critical area does not only represent the vent area but also M_{max} (see equation (3.13)). M_{max} depends on the $\frac{4fL}{D}$ and hence A_c is a function of the vent area and $\frac{4fL}{D}$. Thus, $\frac{A}{A_c}$ is the dominant parameter in the problem. The effect of the area on the pressure and other parameters can be examined with various $\frac{A}{A_c}$ for constant $\frac{4fL}{D}$. The effect of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ can be examined when $\frac{4fL}{D}$ and $\frac{A}{A_c}$ are alternated to keep the area constant.

Figure 3.4 describes the pressure ratio as a function of the dimensionless time. For small time ratio the pressure increases in spite the fact that the vacuum is applied. This fact means that the air pressure in the cavity is larger than the ambient. There is no reason to use vacuum in this kind of design. For time ratio larger than one pressure falls rapidly. The maximum pressure is bounded by the line of zero vent as it is expressed by the $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 0$.

Figure 3.5 shows the air mass fraction for different time ratios as a function of the dimensionless time obtained by equation (3.19). The mass fraction decreases as the time ratio increases. Two interesting limiting cases are found when the vents are sealed and when the time ratio is equal to one. As mentioned, when the time ratio is small there is a large resistance to the mass flow and therefore the mass fraction is close to one. In the case $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$ the pressure is constant, therefore the mass flow rate is constant and mass fraction is a linear function of time. The mass fraction for time ratios which are between these limiting cases, zero and one, is bounded by the horizontal and the linear lines. As the time ratio becomes large, the air mass fraction exponentially decreases.

Figures 3.7 and 3.8 describes the pressure and the mass fraction at the 90% of the piston stroke respectively. These Figures demonstrate that once the vent area reaches the critical value the mass fraction in the cavity remains almost constant. For larger values of the vent area the residual mass increases almost linearly with the time ratio.

For a large time ratio, the pressure in the cylinder drops to a very low value after a short dimensionless time. For example, in the case of $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 4$, the pressure falls to 20% of the initial value after 35% of the stroke as shown in Figure 3.4. In this case the choking condition is not valid. In this model, the flow is assumed to be choked. Once the pressure ratio is lower than the critical ratio the flow is not choked any more and the Mach number depends on the pressure ratio. When this happens, the objective of the vacuum pumping is already achieved even though the mass flow is reduced somewhat.

Typical values for $\frac{4fL}{D}$ can range between 1 and 280 with corresponding values of the M_{in} of 0.51 and 0.05, respectively. A simplified equation can be obtained for the critical duct area at which the pressure stays constant during the injection period. The term in the square brackets of equation (3.12) is on the order of one. Equating the time ratio to one and using equation (3.12) yields

$$t_{max} = \frac{V(0)}{A_c c M_{in}}. \quad (3.21)$$

For atmospheric conditions the speed of sound is about, c , 300 m/sec (11811 in/sec). Thus equation (3.21) obtains the form describing the critical area

$$A_c = \frac{V(0)}{c t_{max} M_{in}}. \quad (3.22)$$

Note that equation (3.22) has similarity to those discussed in the introduction (since $c \propto \sqrt{T}$). Equation (3.22) is useful for the designer.

The procedure to calculate the required duct area:

1. calculate the volume of the cold chamber, runner and die cavity,
2. the condition that no premature freezing occurs determines the filling time of the process, t_{max} ,
3. calculate $\frac{4fL}{D}$ as discussed in (Jeppson 1976),

4. use the $\frac{4fL}{D}$ to get M_{in} from Figure 3.6 as obtained by plotting equation (3.7),
5. use equation (3.22) to get the critical area.
6. chose the desired mass fraction at 90% of the stroke,
7. get the required $\frac{A}{A_C}$ from Figure 3.8, and
8. use the information from Figure 3.8 to get the pressure at 90% of the stroke from Figure 3.7.

From Figures 3.7 and 3.8 or from a detailed calculation one finds that the pressure ratio drops rapidly when the time ratio $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$ exceeds the value one. Example: Assume $\frac{4fL}{D}$ equal 7. M_{in} is equal to 0.3 (see Figure 3.6), the volume $V(0)$ to be 150 cm^3 , and $t_{max} = 0.01$ second. Figure 3.6 and (3.22) determines the critical area of the vent to be 1.67 cm^2 .

3.5 Summary

A simple model is proposed which predicts the pressure variations in the die as a function of time. The critical vent area concept should be helpful to achieve a significant reduction in the air entrainment in vacuum venting.

Figure 3.4: The pressure ratio profiles as a function of the dimensionless time

Figure 3.5: The mass fraction profiles as a function of the dimensionless time

Figure 3.6: The Mach number and the pressure ratio, $\frac{P_{vacuum}}{P_c}$, as a function $\frac{4fL}{D}$

Figure 3.7: The pressure ratio at 90% of the dimensionless time as a function of the area ratio

Figure 3.8: The area ratio as a function of the mass fraction at 90% of the dimensionless time

Chapter 4

AIR VENTING

4.1 Introduction

The most widely used mode of operation is when the vent is open to the atmosphere. This method referred to herein as air venting, is useful when the gas/liquid metal mixing is not significant. This kind of operation is the cheapest and the simplest.

In the early days of die casting the need for venting was not clear. The first development started with the overflow. The overflow volume attaches to the cavity which the air and the excess liquid metal (sacrificed material) are supposed to fill. In this method the pressure of the gases/air is large and, therefore, the volume is reduced in the next stage of development. the overflows were connected to the atmosphere to minimize the back pressure. The design of the opening is such that caused the liquid metal to freeze before it reaches to the open atmosphere.

In some designs, air venting yields good results while in others the results are not satisfactory i.e. too much porosity. An explanation of this inconsistency lies in the fact that the design of a venting system has not been well established until now. An analysis of the air venting yields a solution for the required minimum vent area, and finding this area is the objective of this chapter.

4.2 The Model

Figure 4.1: A schematic of an actual air venting in pressure die casting

In Figure 4.1 a schematic diagram of a die casting system with an air vent is shown. The following model is proposed. The main resistance to the flow is assumed to be in the venting system; therefore, the cold chamber (unfilled volume of the shot sleeve), the die cavity with the runner are combined and called the cylinder. A piston moving with a known velocity pushes the liquid metal and both of them propel the air through a long duct. The liquid metal can be considered to be part of the piston (see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: A simplified model for air venting

Equation (3.1) also describes the air volume in the cylinder during the time when the piston moves. The air mass at any particular time in the cylinder is given by equation

(3.2). The relationship between the pressure and the temperature are also assumed to be isentropic and given by equation (3.3). Hence, equation (3.4) is also applicable in this case.

The flow is also, in this case, approximated as Fanno flow. The Mach numbers at the entrance and exit of the duct are unknown when the flow is not choked. To determine the Mach numbers two equations must be solved. The chosen equations are combinations of the momentum and energy equations in terms of the Mach numbers. These equations, which include the characteristic of Fanno flow, are (Shapiro 1953, pages 84–85)

$$\frac{4fL}{D} = \left[\frac{4fL_{max}}{D} \right]_{M_{in}} - \left[\frac{4fL_{max}}{D} \right]_{M_{exit}} \quad (4.1)$$

and

$$\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)} = \frac{P_{exit}}{P_{0exit}} \frac{P_{0exit}}{P_0(t)} \quad (4.2)$$

or in terms of Mach number

$$\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)} = \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{exit}^2 \right]^{\frac{k}{1-k}} \frac{M_{in}}{M_{exit}} \sqrt{\left[\frac{1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{exit}^2}{1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{in}^2} \right]^{\frac{k+1}{k-1}}} \quad (4.3)$$

where:

$$\frac{4fL}{D} = \frac{1 - M^2}{kM^2} + \frac{k+1}{2k} \ln \left[\frac{(k+1)M^2}{2 \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M^2 \right)} \right]. \quad (4.4)$$

and

- D duct hydraulic diameter,
- L length or equivalent length,
- L_{max} maximum length in which the flow is not choked,
- M_{exit} Mach number at the duct exit,
- M_{in} Mach number at the duct entrance, and
- P_{exit} pressure at the duct exit.

Equations (4.1) and (4.2) show that the Mach numbers depend on the pressure ratio, $\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)}$, and therefore depend on the time. The solution of equations (4.1) and (4.2) for given set $\frac{4fL}{D}$ and $\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)}$ yields different Mach numbers. A special case is where $\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)} = 1$ and $\frac{4fL}{D}$ can be any value. In that case, the Mach numbers are equal to zero.

The term $\frac{4fL}{D}$ is very large for small values of the entrance Mach number. The numerical solution of equations (4.1) and (4.2) requires keeping many digits into the calculations. Instead, these equations can be solved approximately for small values of the Mach numbers. Equation (4.1) can be approximated as

$$\frac{4fL}{D} = \frac{1}{k} \frac{M_{exit}^2 - M_{in}^2}{M_{exit}^2 M_{in}^2} \quad (4.5)$$

and equation (4.3) as

$$\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)} = \frac{M_{in}}{M_{exit}}. \quad (4.6)$$

The solution of the last two equations (4.5) and (4.6) yields

$$M_{in} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \left[\frac{P_{exit}}{P_0(t)}\right]^2}{k \frac{4fL}{D}}}. \quad (4.7)$$

This solution is used for $M_{in} < 0.00286$. The error in the calculations of M_{in} depends on $\frac{4fL}{D}$. This relative error is found to be bounded by 2%.

The mass flow rate can be written

$$\dot{m}_{in} = P_0(0) A M_{max} \frac{M_{in}(t)}{M_{max}} \left(\frac{P_0(0)}{P_0(t)}\right)^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT_0(0)}} f[M_{in}(t)] \quad (4.8)$$

where:

$$f[M_{in}(t)] = \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} (M_{in}(t))^2\right]^{\frac{-(k+1)}{2(k-1)}} \quad (4.9)$$

and M_{max} is the maximum entrance Mach number at the specific duct (see section 3.2 equation 3.7). The mass balance of the air in the piston and the cavity is given by equation 3.10.

4.3 Solution

Substituting equation (3.5) and (4.8) into (3.10) yields

$$\left[\bar{P}\right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{1}{k} \frac{V(t)}{\bar{P}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dt} + \frac{dV(t)}{dt} \right\} + \frac{V(0)}{t_c} \bar{M} f(M) \left[\bar{P}\right]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

where:

$$t_c \approx \frac{m(0)}{\dot{m}_{in}^*}, \quad (4.11)$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{P_0(t)}{P_0(0)}, \quad (4.12)$$

$$\dot{m}_{in}^* \approx AM_{max} P_0(0) \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT_0(0)}} \quad (4.13)$$

and

$$\bar{M} = \frac{M_{in}(t)}{M_{max}}. \quad (4.14)$$

$m(0)$ is the initial mass of the air in the cylinder and $\dot{m}_{in}^*$ is the approximated mass flow rate when the flow is first choked and the pressure and the temperature remain in their initial state.

The parameter t_c represents the approximate time it would take to evacuate the cylinder at the constant flow rate which is obtained when the maximum Mach number is first reached. Note that this characteristic time is different from the one in equation (3.12). Equation (4.10) is an ordinary differential equation and can be rearranged

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{dt} = \frac{k \left(\frac{1}{t_{max}} - \frac{1}{t_c} \bar{M} f(M_{in}) \bar{P}^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} \right)}{1 - \frac{t}{t_{max}}} \bar{P}. \quad (4.15)$$

Dimensionless time is defined by equation (3.16). Substituting equation (3.16) into (4.15) yields

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{d\bar{t}} = \frac{k \left(1 - \frac{t_{max}}{t_c} \bar{M} f(M_{in}) \bar{P}^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} \right)}{1 - \bar{t}} \bar{P}. \quad (4.16)$$

The solution of equation (4.16) can be obtained by numerical integration. For a vent area equal to zero the solution is the same as (3.18) in the previous chapter. The residual mass fraction in the cavity as a function of time can be determined by using (3.19).

4.4 Results and Discussion

The results of a numerical evaluation of the equations in the preceding section are presented in Figures 4.3 through 4.8. Figure 4.3 illustrates the variation with time of the pressure $\bar{P}$ in the cylinder, Figure 4.5 shows the variation of the Mach number M_{exit} at the exit of the duct. Figure 4.7 exhibits the variations of the air mass fraction in the cylinder as a function of the dimensionless time. Figure 4.4, 4.6 and 4.8 present the same parameters for the condition that 0.9 of the dimensionless time, $\frac{t}{t_{max}}$, is elapsed or that the process has completed 0.9 of its strokes.

The influencing parameters in the process are the area ratio, $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and the parameter $\frac{4fL}{D}$ characterizing the duct. The critical area, A_c , is the area which makes the time ratio $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$. Figure 4.3a and 4.3b demonstrate that the influence of the parameter $\frac{4fL}{D}$ on pressure development in the cylinder is quite small. The influence of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ is larger on the exit Mach number, M_{exit} , and smaller on the residual air mass in the cylinder as shown in Figures 4.4 and 4.6, respectively. Choked flow, occurring when the exit Mach number, M_{exit} , reaches a value one, is obtained during the piston stroke only for an area ratio smaller than one according to Figure 4.6a.

The dimensionless area equal to one is an artificial breakeven point. The line that represents $\frac{A}{A_C} = 1$ is almost straight. In vacuum venting there is a clear critical vent area whereas in atmospheric venting there is no such clear distinction. It should be noted that t_c in air venting is slightly different from that in vacuum venting by a factor of $f(M_{max})$. This factor has significance when the Mach number is large for a small $\frac{4fL}{D}$ and a small $\frac{A}{A_C}$ as can be observed from Figure 4.5. The definition is chosen here based on the idea

that for a small Mach number the factor $f(M_{max})$ can be ignored. In the majority of cases the M_{max} is small.

Figure 4.3 describes the pressure as a function of the dimensionless time for various values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and two values of $\frac{4fL}{D}$. In air venting, the pressure in the cylinder is initially built up before the air starts to flow out. The built-up pressure is a function of the resistance to the flow in the venting system. The resistance is a function of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and $\frac{4fL}{D}$. For large values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ the built up pressure increases the volume flow rate of the air until a quasi steady state is reached. This quasi steady state is achieved when the volumetric air flow rate out is equal to volume pushed by the piston. The pressure and the mass flow rate are maintained after equilibrium is reached. For small values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ there is no equilibrium stage. When $\frac{A}{A_C}$ is greater than one the pressure is concave up, and when $\frac{A}{A_C}$ is less than one the pressure is concave down as shown in Figure 4.3a and 4.3b, which were obtained by an integration of equation (4.16). Comparison between Figure 4.3a and 4.3b demonstrates that $\frac{4fL}{D}$ has no significant effect on the pressure.

The maximum pressure is achieved in the limiting case when the vents are sealed. In Figure 4.3a this is shown by the line of $\frac{A}{A_C} = 0$. In this case, no air mass leaves and therefore the air mass in the cylinder is constant or the air mass fraction is equal to one. In this case the entrance Mach number is zero. The pressure remains atmospheric when the vent area is very large and there is no resistance in the duct. Except for the initial part of the stroke, the pressure remains constant as it is in Bennett's model ((Bennett 1990).

Figure 4.4a describes the final pressure ratio at 90% of the stroke as a function of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ for various values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and Figure 4.4b describes the final pressure ratio as a function of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ for $\frac{4fL}{D} = 50$. The final pressure ratio also is referred herein as the pressure. The final pressure depends strongly on the $\frac{A}{A_C}$ as is described in Figure 4.4a. The pressure

at 90% is not affected by $\frac{4fL}{D}$ except for small values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$, where the entrance Mach number is affected by $\frac{4fL}{D}$. The final pressure increase about 85% when $\frac{A}{A_C} = 1$ which is a breakeven point. The final pressure remains constant after $\frac{A}{A_C}$ reaches the value of 1.2.

Figure 4.5 describes the Mach number at the exit of the duct as a function of the dimensionless time for various values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and, where $\frac{4fL}{D} = 5$ and 100. The flow is choked only for small dimensionless area, $\frac{A}{A_C} < 1$. The flow is not choked when the flow is in a quasi steady state. The choking condition develops when the pressure is increased to more than twice the ambient pressure. This happens only after about half of the stroke occurs when $\frac{A}{A_C}$ is small. The choking condition is obtained earlier for smaller $\frac{4fL}{D}$. Choked flow is undesirable since it results in a larger residual air mass according to Figure 4.8a and 4.8b.

Figure 4.6a describes the exit Mach number at 90% of the piston stroke for various $\frac{A}{A_C}$ as a function $\frac{4fL}{D}$. Figure 4.6b describes the exit Mach number as function of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ for $\frac{4fL}{D} = 50$. The flow is choked for small value of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ and when $\frac{A}{A_C} < 1.2$. The flow for $\frac{A}{A_C} > 1.2$ is not choked regardless of how short the duct is. The flow is choked for small values of the dimensionless area and $\frac{4fL}{D}$. The flow stops being choked for $\frac{A}{A_C} < 1$ when $\frac{4fL}{D}$ has a larger value than the critical point which depends on $\frac{A}{A_C}$. The flow is then not choked because it requires a very high pressure to achieve the choking condition which is not obtained at 0.9 of the stroke. This is described clearly, for example, by the line of $\frac{A}{A_C} = 0.5$ in Figure 4.6a.

Figures 4.7a and 4.7b describe the mass fraction as a function of the dimensionless time for various values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ and, when $\frac{4fL}{D} = 5$ and 100. The mass fraction falls between two boundaries: the first, no vent area, value equal one, and the second, the vent area is large, which means no resistance to the flow. For small values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$, the mass fraction changes very little which means very little air flow out. For large values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$, the pressure

remains constant at 1 atmosphere. Therefore the mass flow rate, for values of $\frac{A}{A_C}$ larger than one, is almost constant except at the initial time. Figures 4.7a and 4.7b are very similar which demonstrate that $\frac{4fL}{D}$ has a small effect on the mass fraction.

Figure 4.8a describes the mass fraction at 0.9 of the stroke for various dimensionless area ratios as a function of $\frac{4fL}{D}$. Except to small values of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ the mass fraction is invariant. Figure 4.8b describes the mass fraction for $\frac{4fL}{D} = 50$ as a function of $\frac{A}{A_C}$. The mass fraction is a strong function of $\frac{A}{A_C}$. A conclusion can be drawn that mass fraction does not change above $\frac{A}{A_C} = 1.2$. This means that a die does not need a vent to have dimensionless area larger than 1.2.

A simplified equation can be obtained for the critical duct area at which the pressure stays constant during the injection period. Equating the time ratio $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$ to one and using equation (4.11) yields

$$t_{max} = \frac{V(0)}{A_c c M_{max}}, \quad (4.17)$$

where c is the speed of sound and is a function of the air temperature when $M=1$. An estimate of the speed of sound in this condition, c , is about 350 m/sec. Thus equation (4.17) obtains the form describing the critical area follows:

$$A_c = \frac{V(0)}{c t_{max} M_{max}}. \quad (4.18)$$

Equation (4.18) is useful for the designer.

The procedure to calculate the required duct area:

1. calculate the volume of the cold chamber (unfilled volume of the shot sleeve), runner and die cavity,
2. determine the filling time of the process, t_{max} the condition that no premature freezing occurs.

3. calculate $\frac{4fL}{D}$ as discussed on page 23,
4. use the $\frac{4fL}{D}$ to get M_{max} from Figure 3.6,
5. use equation (4.18) to get the critical area, A_c ,
6. choose the desired mass fraction at 90% of the stroke,
7. get the required $\frac{A}{A_c}$ from Figure 4.8b, and
8. use the $\frac{A}{A_c}$ from Figure 4.8b to get the pressure at 90% of the stroke from Figure 4.4b.

4.5 Summary

A simple model is proposed which predicts the pressure variations in the die as a function of time. Similar concept of critical vent area have been found to be the controlling parameter on the mass flow rate from the cavity. This parameter can be helpful in designing mold in the industry.

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.3: The pressure ratio as a function of the dimensionless time

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.4: The pressure ratio at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.5: The exit Mach number as a function of the dimensionless time

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.6: The exit Mach number at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.7: The mass fraction as a function of the dimensionless time

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 4.8: The mass fraction at 90% of the piston stroke

Chapter 5

TWO CHAMBER ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

In the previous analyses (Chapters 3 and 4) the shot sleeve, runner and die are combined into one cylinder. The assumption of equal pressure in the shot sleeve and the die cavity is checked in this Chapter. Examination of a typical design shows that the gate creates a resistance to the air flow in the same order of magnitude as the vent and the resistance in other cross sections is insignificant. Therefore, it is assumed that two chambers with uniform pressure exist; one which includes the shot sleeve and the runner and the second the die cavity. The combined resistance of the vent and gate is addressed here.

This analysis provides information on the requirements for the gate area from the point of view of the gas/air pressure variations. This requirement on the gate is not the only one but it is the minimum from the air pressure point of view. Other requirements, such as maximum velocity of liquid metal, have to be considered. Additionally, there are other consequences to minimum gate area beside the air pressure reduction, for example, less resistance to the liquid metal flow. The reduction to the liquid metal flow resistance results in downgrading the required hydraulic pressure on the piston. Larger gate area reduces the restriction to the liquid metal flow. Figure 3.3 demonstrates that changes in air pressure do not greatly contribute to the piston movement resistance. The resistance

to the liquid metal flow and the gravitational forces are the main contributions. Keeping the gate area above a certain value will reduce the air pressure and it also reduces the resistance to liquid metal flow and hence the required piston force.

The gate geometry is also determined by other factors such as the trimming requirements. To minimize the secondary work the gate has to be narrow so that it preferably breaks at a particular point. A casting with a wide gate tends to break inside the cast. A typical value of the gate width is in order of 0.1cm and the largest recommended is double this size.

In order to optimize conditions for die casting, the die caster needs the results of an analysis in a form which is easy to use. Presently, there are only models which address the vent area. One of the motivations of this work is to produce simple graphs or formulas for the designer which address requirements for the gate geometrical parameters.

5.2 The Model

Figure 5.1: A schematic of actual die casting for two chamber analysis

The physical situation is described by Figures 5.1. The shot sleeve and the runner are combined to be the cylinder. The die cavity, called the (second) chamber, is connected

on one end to the cylinder through the gate and on the other end to the venting system. The duct in Figure 5.2 connecting the cylinder with the chamber represents the gate. The piston moving with a prescribed velocity pushes the liquid metal and both of them propel air through the chamber and later through a long duct, the vent. The piston velocity is assumed to be constant for the duration of the process considered here. This restriction is less limiting than in the two previous Chapters since only part of the total piston stroke is considered here. Moreover, the piston speed when the shot sleeve and runner are filled with metal is almost constant.

Figure 5.2: A simplified model for two chambers analysis

The equation that describes the air volume in the cylinder during the time when the piston moves can be written in the following form:

$$V_1(t) = V_1(0) \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{maxC}} \right) \quad (5.1)$$

where:

- t time measured from the blockage of pouring hole to time the liquid metal first reaches the gate.
- t_{maxC} cylinder filling time, the time for the liquid metal to reach the gate.
- V_1 air volume in the cylinder cavity, and
- 0 signifies initial time of the air.

t_{maxC} is different from the filling time in the the two previous two Chapters. t_{maxC} is primarily a function of the solidification process and the ratio of the shot sleeve volume plus runner volume to the die cavity volume. The chamber volume is constant during the process considered here and it is

$$V_2(t) = V_2(0) \quad (5.2)$$

where:

V_2 chamber volume cavity.

The air masses at any time in the cylinder and chamber are given by

$$m_i(t) = \frac{P_i(t)V_i(t)}{RT_i(t)} \quad i=1,2 \quad (5.3)$$

where:

P air pressure in the cylinder or chamber,

T air temperature in the cylinder or chamber,

m air mass in cylinder or chamber,

Subscripts

i indicates either the cylinder or chamber,

1 indicates the cylinder, and

2 indicates the chamber.

The pressures in the cylinder and chamber are assumed to be uniform.

Isentropic relationship can be assumed (see discussion in Chapter 3 on page 17) to describe the states in the cylinder and chamber and described by equation (3.3).

Substituting equation (3.3) into equation (5.3) yields

$$m_i(t) = \frac{P_i(0)V_i(t)}{RT_i(0)} \left[\frac{P_i(t)}{P_i(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \quad (5.4)$$

Differentiation of equation (5.4) with respect to time for the cylinder yields

$$\frac{dm_1(t)}{dt} = \frac{m_1(0)}{V_1(0)} \left(\frac{P_1(t)}{P_1(0)} \right)^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{1}{k} \frac{V_1(t)}{P_1(t)} \frac{dP_1(t)}{dt} + \frac{dV_1(t)}{dt} \right\} \quad (5.5)$$

and for the chamber yields

$$\frac{dm_2(t)}{dt} = \frac{m_2(0)}{k} \left(\frac{P_2(t)}{P_2(0)} \right)^{\frac{1-k}{k}} \frac{d \left(\frac{P_2(t)}{P_2(0)} \right)}{dt}. \quad (5.6)$$

To obtain the Mach numbers equation (4.1) and equation (4.2) are needed to be solved for every duct. A discussion of the flow in the vent and runner is given in Chapter 4 page 32.

The mass flow rate can be written

$$\dot{m}_{in\ i} = P_{0i}(0) A_i M_{max\ i} \frac{M_{in}(t)}{M_{max\ i}} \left(\frac{P_{0i}(0)}{P_{0i}(t)} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT_{0i}(0)}} f[M_{in}(t)_i] \quad (5.7)$$

where $f[M_{in}(t)_i]$ is given by equation (4.9) and M_{max} is the maximum entrance Mach number for a specific duct.

The mass balance of the air in the cylinder yields

$$\frac{dm_1}{dt} + \dot{m}_{in1} = 0 \quad (5.8)$$

and the mass balance on the chamber yields

$$\frac{dm_2}{dt} + \dot{m}_{in2} - \dot{m}_{in1} = 0. \quad (5.9)$$

5.3 Solution

Substituting equation (5.5), (5.6) and (5.7) into (5.8) and (5.9) yields

$$\left[\bar{P}_1 \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{V_1(t)}{k \bar{P}_1} \frac{d \bar{P}_1}{dt} + \frac{dV_1}{dt} \right\} + \frac{V_1(0)}{t_{c1}} \bar{M}_1 f(M_1) \left[\bar{P}_1 \right]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} = 0 \quad (5.10)$$

$$\frac{1}{k} \left[\bar{P}_2 \right]^{\frac{1-k}{k}} \frac{d \bar{P}_2}{dt} + \frac{\bar{M}_2 f \{M_{in2}(t)\}}{t_{c2}} \left[\bar{P}_2 \right]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} - \frac{m_1(0)}{m_2(0)} \frac{\bar{M}_1 f \{M_{in1}(t)\}}{t_{c1}} \left[\bar{P}_1 \right]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} = 0 \quad (5.11)$$

where:

$$t_{ci} \approx \frac{m(0)}{\dot{m}_{in\ i=1,2}^*}, \quad (5.12)$$

$$\bar{P}_i = \frac{P_0(t)}{P_0(0)_{i=1,2}}, \quad (5.13)$$

$$\dot{m}_{in_i}^* = A_i M_{max_i} P_0(0)_i \sqrt{\frac{k}{RT_0(0)_{i=1,2}}} \quad (5.14)$$

and

$$\bar{M}_i = \frac{M_{in}(t)}{M_{max \ i=1,2}}. \quad (5.15)$$

$\dot{m}_{in}^*$ is the approximate mass flow rate when the flow is first choked and the pressure and temperature remain in their initial values.

The parameter t_{c1} represents the ratio between the air mass in the cylinder and the air mass flow rate at the gate when the stagnation temperature and stagnation pressure remain constant. Equations (5.10) and (5.11) can be written as

$$\frac{V_1(0) \left[1 - \frac{t}{t_{maxC}}\right]}{P_1} \frac{d\bar{P}_1}{dt} - k \frac{V_1(0)}{t_{maxC}} + \frac{kV_1(0)}{t_{c1}} \bar{M}_1 f\{M_{in1}(t)\} [\bar{P}_1]^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} = 0 \quad (5.16)$$

and equation (5.11)

$$\frac{d\bar{P}_2}{dt} + \frac{k\bar{M}_2 f\{M_{in2}(t)\}}{t_{c2}} [\bar{P}_2]^{\frac{k-1}{2k}} - \frac{m_1(0) k\bar{M}_1 f\{M_{in1}(t)\}}{m_2(0) t_{c1}} [\bar{P}_1]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} [\bar{P}_2]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} = 0. \quad (5.17)$$

A dimensionless time can be defined as

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{t_{maxC}} \quad (5.18)$$

Substituting equation (5.18) into (5.16) and (5.17) and rearranging yields

$$\frac{d\bar{P}_1}{d\bar{t}} = \frac{k \left(1 - \frac{t_{maxC}}{t_{c1}} g\{M_{in1}(t)\} [\bar{P}_1]^{\frac{k-1}{2k}}\right)}{1 - \bar{t}} \bar{P}_1 \quad (5.19)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{P}_2}{d\bar{t}} = k \frac{m_1(0) t_{maxC}}{m_2(0) t_{c1}} g\{M_{in1}(t)\} [\bar{P}_1]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} [\bar{P}_2]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} - k \frac{t_{maxC}}{t_{c2}} g\{M_{in2}(t)\} [\bar{P}_2]^{\frac{k+1}{2k}} \quad (5.20)$$

where:

$$g[M_{in}(t)] = \frac{M_{in}(t)}{M_{max}} \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{2} (M_{in}(t))^2\right]^{\frac{-(k+1)}{2(k-1)}}. \quad (5.21)$$

A solution to equations (5.19) and (5.20) can be obtained by numerical integration.

The fraction of the air mass in the cylinder as a function of time can be determined by using (5.1), (5.3) and (3.3)

$$\bar{m}_1 = \bar{P}_1^{\frac{1}{k}} (1 - \bar{t}), \quad (5.22)$$

and for the chamber

$$\bar{m}_2 = \bar{P}_2^{\frac{1}{k}}, \quad (5.23)$$

where:

$$\bar{m}_i = \frac{m_i(t)}{m_i(0)}. \quad (5.24)$$

5.4 Results and Discussion

The results are presented in Figures 5.3-5.13. Figures 5.3-5.9 describe the pressure, Mach number and air mass in the chamber and cylinder as a function of dimensionless time. Figures 5.10-5.12 describe the same properties at 90% of piston stroke as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. Figure 5.13 describes the ratio of the pressure in the cylinder to the pressure in the chamber when the 0.9 of the piston stroke is elapsed. Note that 90% of the piston stroke is different from the one that is defined in Chapters 3 and 4. Here, 90% of the piston stroke is referred to the filling of the shot sleeve whereas in the previous two Chapters it also includes the filling of the die cavity. Figures 5.3a and 5.3b describe the pressure variations in the cylinder and chamber for vacuum venting, and Figures 5.4a and 5.4b for air venting in the cylinder and chamber, respectively. Figures 5.5a and 5.5b describe the gate exit and entrance Mach number for different area ratios $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ for vacuum venting and Figures 5.6a-5.7b describe the Mach number for air venting. Figures 5.8a, 5.8b, 5.9a and 5.9b are the same as 5.3a, 5.3b, 5.4a and 5.4b but describe the mass fraction instead of the pressure. Figures 5.10a and 5.10b describe the pressure at 90% of the stroke in the

cylinder and chamber, respectively. Figure 5.11 describes the exit Mach number. Figure 5.12 describes the mass fraction in the cylinder and chamber. Figures 5.13 describes the ratio between the pressure in the chamber and the pressure in the cylinder as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$.

It is important to point out the significance of the time ratios $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{c1}}$ and $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{c2}}$. These parameters represent the ratio between the time of the actual filling process and the approximate time which would be required to evacuate the cylinder or chamber when the maximum Mach number and the pressure and temperature remains in their initial state. This parameter also represents the dimensionless area, $\frac{A}{A_C}$ according to the following equation

$$\frac{t_{max i}}{t_{c i}} = \frac{A_i}{A_{C i}}, \quad (5.25)$$

where:

A duct cross sectional area

A_c critical exit duct cross sectional area which makes $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = 1$.

Equation (5.25) is obtained from equation (5.12).

$\frac{t_{max}}{t_{c1}}$ and $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{c2}}$ are also related to the total air mass in the cavity, as the following

$$\frac{t_{max}}{t_c} = \frac{t_{c2}}{t_{max}} + \frac{t_{c1}}{t_{max}} \frac{\dot{m}_{in}^*|_1}{\dot{m}_{in}^*|_2} \quad (5.26)$$

where:

$\dot{m}_{in}^*$ mass flow rate at the gate, and

t_c t_c for the whole system (it is the same as t_c in Chapters 3 and 4).

The effect of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ has found to be secondary in Chapter 4 and will not be in the focus here. Since the required vent area was treated in the two preceding Chapters, the study here is concentrated on the minimum required gate area. It has to be noted that when the piston stroke is completed the process continues and the two previous Chapters are applicable.

Figures 5.3a and 5.4a describe the pressure variations in the cylinder for vacuum venting and air venting with a sufficient vent area $\frac{A_2}{A_{C2}} = 2.0$ as a function of $\bar{t}$. The pressure in the cylinder is similar for both cases. These results are similar to the results obtained in the previous two Chapters which can be seen by comparison of the two cases. The difference between air venting and vacuum venting appears at large values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. The pressure in vacuum venting can fall below the atmospheric pressure as it seen from Figure 5.3a but the lowest pressure in air venting is the atmospheric pressure. The similarity between both cases is explained by the fact that air pressure in the chamber is bounded between 0.5 and 1.2 atmospheres in the extreme cases as shown in Figures 5.3b and 5.4b. Moreover, most cases the pressure in the chamber is very close to atmospheric pressure in the initial part of the stroke and for a large range of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$.

Figures 5.3b and 5.4b describe the pressure variations in the chamber for vacuum venting and air venting with a sufficient vent area $\frac{A_2}{A_{C2}} = 2.0$ as a function of $\bar{t}$. In vacuum venting, the pressure in the chamber decreases at first and after an half of the stroke or more, the pressure increases for small values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. In air venting the pressure in the chamber increases with time. For $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} > 1$, the pressure is concave down and for $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} > 1$ the pressure is concave up. This indicates that mass flow rate at the vent is larger for $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} > 1$.

Figures 5.5a and 5.6a describe the gate exit Mach number for vacuum venting and air venting, respectively. In both cases the flow is not choked for large $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ and is only choked for $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} < 1$. The similarity is due to the fact that the pressure is bounded between 0.5 and 1.2 atmospheres in the extreme cases as shown in Figures 5.3b and 5.4b. The difference between the two cases is that in air venting the choking occurs at a later stage. This is expected since the air pressure in the chamber is higher for air venting. In Figures 5.7a and 5.7b the vent Mach numbers at the exit and entrance of the vent are described for air venting. The Mach number is small for all cases and the flow can be considered

incompressible. The Mach number for large $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ increases rapidly at first but less in later stages. For small values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ the Mach number is concave up.

Figures 5.8a and 5.9a exhibit the mass fraction in the cylinder for air venting and vacuum venting, respectively. For large values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ the mass fraction decreases linearly with time and for small values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ it approaches one. Figure 5.8b describes the mass fraction in the chamber for vacuum venting. The mass fraction is concave up which indicates larger mass flow rate in the initial and later stages of the stroke. Figures 5.9b describes the mass fraction in the chamber for air venting. The mass fraction is higher than one in all cases. For $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} > 1$ the mass fraction is concave down which indicate larger mass flow rates.

Figure 5.10a describes the pressure at 90% of the piston stroke for air venting and vacuum venting in the cylinder as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. The pressure behaves similarly for both cases. For small values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ the pressure is large and for large values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ the pressure is equal to one or smaller. Figure 5.10b describes the pressure at 90% of the piston stroke for air venting and vacuum venting in the chamber as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. The pressure increases with $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ for both cases and for $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ larger than one the pressure remains almost constant.

Figure 5.11a describes the gate exit Mach number at 90% of the piston stroke for vacuum and air venting as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. For small values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ the flow is choked up to about $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} = 1$. After that the Mach number falls dramatically and thereafter changes very little. Figure 5.11b describes the vent exit Mach number at 90% of the piston stroke for vacuum and air venting as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. For air venting the Mach number reaches a maximum.

Figure 5.12a describes the mass fraction at the 90% of the piston stroke as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ in the cylinder. The mass fraction falls exponentially with $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. When the value

of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}} = 1$, the mass fraction is minimal. This information means that the gate area has to be at least in the magnitude of the critical area, $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$. Figure 5.12b describes the mass fraction at 90% of the piston stroke as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ in the chamber. For values of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ smaller than one in vacuum venting the mass is small while for value $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ larger one the mass fraction is almost constant and equal to 0.8. For air venting the phenomenon is similar but the final value of the mass fraction is about 1.1. The maximum in the mass fraction happens due to release of the mass from the cylinder only in the later stages.

Figure 5.13 describes the ratio between the pressure in the chamber and pressure in the cylinder at 90% of the stroke as a function of $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ for two different $\frac{A_2}{A_{C2}}$. From the figure and detail calculations the pressure ratio is very high for small $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ (< 1) and almost equal to one when $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ is larger than 1.5. The pressure ratio is less than 2 for $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ larger than 0.9. Thus, the assumption of equal pressure in the die and the shot sleeve is very good when $\frac{A_1}{A_{C1}}$ (gate area) is larger than 2. This assumption is better for smaller $\frac{A_2}{A_{C2}}$. For smaller $\frac{A_2}{A_{C2}}$ the resistance in the vent and the gate are large and therefore the pressure difference is smaller.

The procedure to calculate the required duct (gate & vent) area follows:

1. calculate the volume not filled by the liquid metal of the shot sleeve and runner,
2. determine the time of the process, the condition that no premature freezing occurs, t_{maxC} ,
3. calculate $\frac{4fL}{D}$ for the gate and vent
4. use the $\frac{4fL}{D}$ to get M_{max} from Figure 3.6
5. use equation (4.18) to get the critical area, A_c , and
6. choose the gate area to be larger than the critical area.

5.5 Summary

A simple model is proposed which predicts the pressure variations in the cylinder and the chamber as a function of time. The model demonstrates that the pressure in the shot sleeve increases when the gate area is smaller than the critical area and the air is not vented easily. When the gate is larger than the critical area the pressure in the shot sleeve and the die cavity can be assumed to equal.

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.3: The pressure ratios as a function of the dimensionless time in vacuum venting in the cylinder and chamber

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.4: The pressure ratios as a function of the dimensionless time in air venting in the cylinder and chamber

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.5: The Mach number as a function of the dimensionless time for vacuum venting

Figure 5.6: The Mach number as a function of the dimensionless time at air venting for the gate

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.7: The Mach number of the vent as a function of the dimensionless time for air venting

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.8: The mass fraction as a function of the dimensionless time in vacuum venting

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.9: The mass fraction as a function of the dimensionless time in air venting

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.10: The pressure at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.12: The mass fraction at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.11: The exit Mach number at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure a

Figure b

Figure 5.12: The mass fraction at 90% of the piston stroke

Figure 5.13: The mass fraction at 90% of the piston stroke

Chapter 6

PORE-FREE TECHNIQUE

6.1 Introduction

When air venting does not yield sufficient reduction in the porosity, the cavity can be pumped by a vacuum pump through a tank. This happens in very complicated cavity shapes where the gas is entrapped when some sections of the cavity are blocked. Alternative solution besides using a vacuum pump is the Pore Free Technique. In the last three Chapters the gas mass was assumed to be constant i.e. no reactions. In this chapter the Pore Free Technique is analyzed. The largest mass change happens due to the oxygenation. Beside the analysis of this technique, this model provides a tool to analyze the reaction including nitrogen release and oxidation of the liquid metal.

In the Pore Free Technique, oxygen is introduced into the cavity to replace the nitrogen and to react with the liquid metal. In the case of aluminum the reaction is $2Al(l) + \frac{3}{2}O_2(g) \rightarrow Al_2O_3(l)$ in which the aluminum oxide is dispersed in the metal. A typical percentage of the aluminum oxide in the aluminum is 0.24% and it does not affect the properties of the products (Kaye and Street 1982).

The Pore Free Technique has been used since the early 1970s (Herrschaft 1976). This method is used mainly by Japanese die casters (e.g. Fuso Light Alloys LTD) but not used by many others since they have encountered some difficulties. The analysis here aims to

Figure 6.1: A general description of the Pore Free Technique

provide general rules as to when this method is appropriate and what the parameters that affect oxidation are. It also addresses how the parameters can be modified so that the technique will yield better results.

6.2 The Model

A general description of the process is given in Figure 6.1. As oxygen is introduced to the die cavity it flushes out the nitrogen through the vent as illustrated in Figure 6.1. The oxygen is transferred from the bulk to the interface where the oxygen undergoes an heterogeneous reaction which creates an oxide. As a result an oxide layer is created in which practically no more mass transfer occurs. The fact that this oxide is found almost uniformly (Kaye and Street 1982) in the aluminum after the solidification suggests that the oxide layer is broken by the turbulence in the liquid and replaced by a fresh layer. Thus, the mass transfer can be represented as transfer through a series of resistances (see Figure 6.2). A general discussion of this kind of problems is found in Cussler (1984). The difference in the oxygen chemical potential between the gas phase and the liquid-phase (aluminum) is very large (ASM 1987); therefore, the reaction is instantaneous. Hence,

the resistance to mass transfer occurs in the gas phase and the liquid phase.

Figure 6.2: A scheme of oxygen transfer mechanism

The actual surface of the liquid metal and the percentage to which the surface is replaced are primarily a function of the liquid metal flow rate and the die geometry. The percentage of the replaced area is a measure of the resistance in the liquid phase. The fact that the oxygen oxide concentration in the liquid phase was found almost uniform indicates that the mixing process is very effective. Thus, the resistance to mass transfer occurs only in the gas phase.

Not all the nitrogen is removed from the cavity and cylinder when the oxygen is introduced. Moreover, some nitrogen is released from the liquid metal while solidification occurs. This nitrogen is concentrated close to the interface and creates resistance to oxygen diffusion. The nitrogen concentration does not change significantly; therefore, the total resistance is assumed to be independent of the nitrogen concentration.

The oxygen flux through the oxide layer after a short time is very small and can be neglected (ASM 1987). The oxygen molar flux can be expressed as

$$\dot{n}_{O_2 out} = A_F K_t (C_{bulk} - C^*) \cong A_F K_t C_{bulk} \quad (6.1)$$

In practical situations, the oxygen partial pressure at the liquid metal surface is zero and

thus $C^* = 0$. Estimation of the value of the mass transfer coefficient, K_t , can be achieved by using information available for similar mass transfer processes. A_F is the interface between the liquid metal and the gas.

The equation that describes the oxygen (air) volume in the cylinder cavity during the time when the piston moves is given by equation (3.1). The number of oxygen moles at any particular time in the cylinder, consisting of the cavity, the runner and the shot sleeve is given by

$$n_{O_2}(t) = \frac{P_{O_2}(t)V(t)}{RT(t)} \quad (6.2)$$

where:

P_{O_2} oxygen partial pressure.

The gases in the cylinder undergo an isentropic process under the assumptions that this model is constructed. Hence, the relationship between the pressure and the temperature in the cylinder is:

$$\frac{T(t)}{T(0)} = \left[\frac{P(t)}{P(0)} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \quad (6.3)$$

When the gases are mostly composed of oxygen, equation (6.3) can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{T(t)}{T(0)} \cong \left[\frac{P_{O_2}(t)}{P_{O_2}(0)} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \quad (6.4)$$

Note that the specific heat ratio of oxygen is equal to 1.4. Substituting equation (6.4) into equation (6.2) yields:

$$n_{O_2}(t) = \frac{P_{O_2}(0)V(t)}{RT(0)} \left[\frac{P_{O_2}(t)}{P_{O_2}(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \quad (6.5)$$

Differentiation of equation (6.5) with respect to time yields:

$$\frac{dn_{O_2}(t)}{dt} = C_{O_2}(0) \left[\frac{P_{O_2}(t)}{P_{O_2}(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \left\{ \frac{1}{k} \frac{V(t)}{P_{O_2}(t)} \frac{dP_{O_2}(t)}{dt} + \frac{dV(t)}{dt} \right\} \quad (6.6)$$

where:

$$C_{O_2}(0) = \frac{P_{O_2}(0)}{RT(0)}. \quad (6.7)$$

Combining equation (6.1), (6.4) and (6.7), the oxygen molar flux due to the reaction is:

$$\dot{n}_{O_2 out} = \frac{A_F K_t P_{O_2}(t)}{RT(t)} = \frac{A_F K_t P_{O_2}(0)}{RT(0)} \left[\frac{P_{O_2}(t)}{P_{O_2}(0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}}. \quad (6.8)$$

It is assumed that the oxygen molar flux into the cavity can be neglected. It is also assumed that the flow is choked and the molar flow out through the vent can be neglected. Thus, the molar balance of the oxygen in the cylinder cavity is:

$$\frac{dn_{O_2}(t)}{dt} + \dot{n}_{O_2 out} = 0. \quad (6.9)$$

6.3 Solution

Note that $\frac{dV}{dt}$ according to equation (3.1) is equal to $-\frac{V(0)}{t_{max}}$. Substituting equations (3.1), (6.6) and (6.8) into (6.9) yields:

$$\frac{1}{k} \frac{(1 - \bar{t})}{\bar{P}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{d\bar{t}} - 1 + \frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}} = 0 \quad (6.10)$$

where:

$$t_{cR} = \frac{V(0)}{K_t A_F}, \text{ and} \quad (6.11)$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{P_{O_2}(t)}{P_{O_2}(0)}. \quad (6.12)$$

According to equations (6.3) and (6.4) $\bar{P}$ is also the total pressure ratio. Dimensionless time is defined as:

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{t_{max}}. \quad (6.13)$$

The parameter t_{cR} represents the characteristic time of the reaction to deplete the oxygen when P_{O_2} remains constant. The dimensionless time can be interpreted as a fraction of the volume of the cylinder. Equation (6.10) can be rearranged to be:

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{\bar{P}} = \frac{k d\bar{t}}{(1-\bar{t})} \left(1 - \frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}\right). \quad (6.14)$$

Equation (6.14) can be integrated to yield:

$$\ln \bar{P} = -k \left(1 - \frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}\right) \ln(1 - \bar{t}). \quad (6.15)$$

Thus, the solution of equation (6.10) can be written as:

$$\bar{P} = \{1 - \bar{t}\}^{-k \left(1 - \frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}\right)}. \quad (6.16)$$

The fraction of the oxygen (air) moles left in the cavity as a function of time can be determined by using (3.1), (6.2), (6.4) and (6.16) to be:

$$\bar{n} = \bar{P}^{\frac{1}{k}} (1 - \bar{t}) = \{1 - \bar{t}\}^{\left(\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}\right)} \quad (6.17)$$

where

$$\bar{n} = \frac{n_{O_2}(t)}{n_{O_2}(0)}. \quad (6.18)$$

6.4 Results and Discussion

The results are presented in Figures 6.3 through 6.5. Figure 6.3 describes the pressure ratio variations in the cavity as a function of the dimensionless time. Figure 6.4 describes the oxygen molar fraction as a function of dimensionless time. Figure 6.5 describes the pressure ratio when 0.9 of the piston stroke is elapsed.

Figure 6.3 describes the pressure variations in the Pore Free Technique and vacuum venting. The solid lines are for vacuum venting. They are almost identical to those for the Pore Free Technique when the parameter $\frac{t_{max}}{t_c}$ have equal values. The characteristic times,

t_c , for the two cases are different because they contain different physical properties. t_c is defined by equation (6.11) for the Pore Free Technique and equation (3.12) for vacuum venting. In vacuum venting, t_c is a measure of the time needed to evacuate the cavity when the pressure is maintained constant. t_{cR} is the time to deplete all oxygen in the cylinder due to the reaction. The governing equations 3.11 (for vacuum venting) and 6.10 (for Pore Free Technique) are different equations but it turns out that the two processes are similar. The pressure is maintained constant in both cases when the time ratio is equal to one. In the Pore Free Technique the response is stronger. For example, when this ratio is greater than one the pressure increases for both techniques but is higher in the Pore Free Technique. Also, when the time ratio is less than one, the pressure decreases but is faster in the Pore Free case.

Maximum pressure is achieved in the limiting case when there is no reaction. In Figure 6.3 this is shown by the line $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}} = 0$. In this case the number of the gas moles in the cylinder remains constant or the oxygen fraction is equal to one.

Figure 6.3: The pressure ratio profile as a function of the dimensionless time

The parameter, $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}$, represents the ratio between the time of the actual filling process (solidification) and the characteristic time to deplete the oxygen when the oxygen partial pressure remains constant. This ratio represents the relationship between two effects, the reaction which reduces the pressure and the compression by the piston which increases the pressure. When the ratio is equal to one, the pressure in the cylinder remains constant as indicated by equation (6.16). This is the breakeven point: the pressure will decrease if $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}$ is greater than one, and the pressure will increase if $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}}$ is less than one as shown in Figure 6.3, which was obtained by plotting equation (6.16).

Figure 6.4 shows the oxygen molar fraction for different time ratios as a function of the dimensionless time, $\bar{t}$, obtained by plotting equation (6.17). The mass fraction decreases as the time ratio increases. Two interesting limiting cases are found when there is no reaction and when the time ratio is equal to one. As mentioned, the time ratio is small when the reaction is slow or the actual area of the liquid metal is small. In the case $\frac{t_{max}}{t_{cR}} = 1$ the pressure is constant; therefore, the oxygen depletion rate is constant and the molar fraction is a linear function of time. The molar fraction for time ratios which are between these limiting cases of zero and one is bounded by the horizontal and the linear lines. As the time ratio becomes large, the air molar fraction decreases exponentially.

Figure 6.5 describes the pressure ratio at the 0.9 of the piston stroke. It indicates that a change of $t_{cR} < 1$ to $t_{cR} > 1$ will mean a change from a successful to an unsuccessful operation. This phenomena is magnified by the solidification process. The liquid metal is solidified and an oxide layer is created during injection into the cavity. This layer is not broken when it is solidified. Once this layer is established no "fast" mass transfer occurs. The oxygen in the solid has to be diffused through the oxide layer. The time scale for this mechanism is several orders of magnitude slower (ASM 1987). Moreover, the porosity is already created after the solidification. Thus, desired situations are when the metal is in the liquid stage (large t_{cR}), where the reaction is fast.

Figure 6.4: The molar fraction profile as a function of the dimensionless time

Equation (6.3) is based on an isentropic relationship. Moreover, it is assumed that the gas in the cavity is mostly composed of oxygen. If any of the assumptions on which this model was constructed are not valid, then the flow inside the cylinder is not isentropic. A different relationship between the temperature and the pressure exists. However, for the case where the pressure in the cylinder remains constant, the oxygen depletion rate, $\dot{n}_{O_2 out}$, also remains constant during the filling process and $t_{max} = t_{cR}$. $t_{max} = t_{cR}$ exists for any relationship between the pressure and temperature.

The time ratio is a combination of the solidification time t_{max} and reaction time t_{cR} . The solidification is effected by the heat transfer processes in the cavity and by the super-heating of the liquid metal. Increasing t_{max} can be accomplished by increasing the temperature of the liquid metal. The other solidification parameters cannot be changed very much. The parameter t_{cR} is a function of the turbulence level in the cavity and the resistance to oxygen transfer. Reduction of t_{cR} requires reduction of the nitrogen, which reduces the resistance to oxygen transfer. This can be achieved by longer flushing

Figure 6.5: The pressure ratio at 90% of the piston stroke as a function of the time ratio times and/or better design of the flushing system. A change in the turbulence level can be obtained by changing the flow region, for example, changing the flow from spray to continuous. Hence, time ratio manipulation can be done by altering the design of the flushing system, controlling the flow pattern, and controlling the temperature.

The vacuum venting technique yields good results in many instances provided the design is good. In other cases, when the flow pattern in the cavity is very turbulent and some sections are blocked, the gas is entrapped before the vacuum can take effect. In these cases, the Pore Free method can be a viable solution.

6.5 Summary

One of the proposed ways to reduce the amount of entrained air is to introduce oxygen into the die cavity in where it reacts with the liquid metal. A simple model is proposed which predicts the pressure variations in the die as a function of time. This model should be helpful for choosing the best method to achieve a significant reduction in the air entrainment. Moreover, in cases where the Pore Free Technique is chosen, the parameters

needed to be modified are indicated.

Chapter 7

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF A LIQUID WALL JET INTO STARTING A GASEOUS MEDIUM

7.1 Introduction

In the previous Chapters the flow through the various compounds of die casting arrangement was described in a global manner. Now attention will be focussed on the details of the flow process occurring as a liquid jet enters the die cavity and displaces the gas in the cavity because it can be expected that this plays an important role in the gas entrapment mechanism.

In this work, experiments were conducted to provide information on the entrapment mechanisms and flow patterns. The affecting parameters were examined in typical configurations of die casting. A liquid jet entering into a gaseous medium has two typical configurations, a free jet and a wall jet. The wall jet was chosen here since it appears in many gate designs. The author is not aware of any previous studies dealing with it.

The gate geometry may affect the jet flow pattern. Therefore, three different gates were examined, converged, diverged, and optimized gates. The optimized gate is also a converged gate but the shape is smooth (a third order polynomial was used to shape the

transition of the gate to the die cavity). The time development of the flow rate of the jet also was altered for different runs and it is referred to herein as the velocity function. Additionally, the pressure in the cavity was varied among three levels; atmospheric, and plus or minus ~ 0.2 atmospheres.

7.2 Dimensional Analysis

Eckert (1989) has shown that experiments simulating flow in die casting can be performed with enlarged scale models in order to circumvent the difficulties associated with small dimensions. Water or other nonmetallic fluids can also be used to simulate the liquid metal. As long as one uses a scaled model of a die and makes sure that certain dimensionless parameters in the model experiments have the same values as in an actual die casting process, the results from the experiments will perfectly match the actual die casting process.

One can show that the flow in the model experiment is similar in all details to the flow in a die casting process when three parameters, the Froude, Reynolds and Weber numbers (Fr , Re and We , respectively) are matched and the geometry is similar. The Reynolds number here is based on the hydraulic diameter of the gate as characteristic length. A typical value of Re in die casting is $\sim 10^5$ and a typical value of We is 20×10^3 . The value obtained in the experiment described in this chapter for Re was $0.9 \times 10^5 - 1.3 \times 10^5$ and for We was $15.8 \times 10^3 - 29.7 \times 10^3$. The Froude number in the experiment is larger by a factor of 10 from the typical value obtained in a die casting process. Thus, the parameters obtained in the experiment matched, to a large extent, the parameters in die casting operation. An estimate for this experiment shows that the boundary layer thickness is less than one percent of the jet thickness.

The velocity has approximately the same value whereas the length scale is about 10 times as large for the experiment. The characteristic time of the die casting process

is, therefore, 30 *millisecond*. The above mentioned parameters identify the flow process completely where piston velocity changes simultaneously from rest to a constant value, (V). In the experiments, it takes the piston a finite time, t_0 to reach the constant velocity (see Figure 7.2). In this case, the dimensionless parameter $\frac{t_0 V}{L}$ of the model experiment has also to match that of the actual die casting process to make the flow similar. Measurements in this experiment are restricted to the time between starting the of the jet to the time in which the jet reach the top of the chamber.

7.3 Experimental Apparatus

Experiments were carried out in a vertical test section with a horizontal cylinder assembly, system as shown in Figure 7.1. The experimental layout consisted of a hydraulic pump and an actuator controlled by a wave generator, cylinder assembly, and test section. The cylinder was connected to a runner and gate assembly using copper tubing which incorporated a 90 degree turn to obtain a vertical test section resembling a cold chamber machine. The test section itself was a chamber with transparent plexiglass walls (see Figure 7.4). All components of the apparatus, excluding the hydraulic pump and the wave generator, were securely mounted to a level table to assure stable positioning. The data for this experiment were captured visually using still photography and a high-speed film camera at 400 frames per second.

7.3.1 Controlling apparatus

The hydraulic pump drives the MTS actuator model 244.11S/N248 with a maximum pressure of 20.7 *MPa*. The MTS actuator was connected to the pump by 0.953 *cm* inside diameter hoses about 1.5 *m* long. The Wavetex model 75 arbitrary wave form generator controlled the actuator to achieve a specified velocity function. The velocity functions included a square wave and two constant acceleration velocities (see Figure 7.2). The

Figure 7.1: A schematic of the experimental apparatus

square wave utilized the maximum velocity attainable from the hydraulic pump. The linear increase function (constant acceleration, sometimes referred to as the “parachute” profile) was used to examine the effects of this function on the jet. The “parachute” profile is used to minimize a possible wave formation in the cylinder (also called shot sleeve).

7.3.2 Cylinder & gate assemblies

The cylinder assembly consisted of a stainless steel piston encased in a plexiglass cylinder of 10.16 *cm* in diameter and 25.4 *cm* in length. Two rubber rings were used around the circumference of the piston to assure a tight seal at the interface between the piston and cylinder. The piston and actuator were precisely aligned to insure a tight seal throughout the piston stroke and to minimize the friction in the cylinder. The cylinder was opened to the atmosphere on the backside of the piston to eliminate back pressure. A silicone lubricant was used to diminish the mixing with water. Three valves were located at the end of the cylinder. The larger valve was used to drain the cylinder and fill the test

Figure 7.2: Velocity functions of the plunger used in this experiment

section. The small valve on the cylinder top (see Figure 7.1) allowed air to escape. The lower electrical valve was used to fill the cylinder.

The cylinder assembly was connected to the die cavity via 2.54 *cm* inside diameter copper tubing. The tubing was positioned with only one bend and only one T-connection to reduce the resistance. Two pipes branched from the main tube. One was used to drain the system; the other was used to maintain a constant initial filling height during all of the runs (as shown in figure 7.1). The T-connection was located far from the 90 degree bend to minimize its effects on the water flow. Three separate runner and gate assemblies were used during this experiment.

The three assemblies are shown in Figures 7.3a through 7.3c. The first assembly was designed to produce a uniform velocity profile of the water jet at the gate and was made of fiberglass, referred to herein as runner *A*. The runner in the second and third gate assemblies was made of aluminum. Figure 7.3b shows a diverging runner and Figure 7.3c shows a converging runner. They are referred to herein as runners *B* and *C*, respectively.

The transition from the round copper tubing to the specified exit gate geometry was similar for all the runners. The round tubing was connected to a round-to-square section. The latter was connected to a square section. The square section was connected to the

Figure 7.3: A schematic of the runners

exit, referred herein as the gate. The optimal gate design incorporates a third order polynomial to smooth the transition. The two other gates were designed using straight lines. In the round-to-square part, the rectangular cross-section area was slightly larger than the area of the circular section. The optimum runner was made from three different parts, while the other two were made from one block.

The chamber was constructed of plexiglass to allow external viewing of the flow (see Figure 7.4). There was a different chamber for each runner; each could be rigidly attached to the gate assembly. The chamber volume was designed to be significantly larger than the

Figure 7.4: A schematic of the chambers (all the measurements given herein are in *cm*)

injected liquid jet to minimize influence of the chamber walls on the flow. Every chamber had an air vent on the top to maintain a constant pressure during the filling time. All die chambers had three ports on the side to allow for increasing or decreasing cavity pressure and measurement of the cavity pressure. These ports were located on the side of the die cavity to minimize the effects of air movement. The pressure was measured before each run using a mercury manometer. During the duration of the run, this port was sealed.

7.3.3 Data acquisition

Still photography of the flow was done using a Nikon 35mm camera. The triggering mechanism was mounted on the connecting rod between the hydraulic actuator and the cylinder assembly, as shown in Figure 7.1. Photos were taken in a completely dark room. The shutter of the camera was held open via remote trigger throughout the duration of the run. The piston movement activated a flash by triggering the switch attached to a stationary rod. The switch can be moved along a track on the rod to take pictures at different locations of the jet in different runs. The camera was attached to an arm

mounted to the table to have pictures from the same location for every run. This arm was hinged to allow easy access to the test section and to allow for adequate removal of the camera mounting system.

Figure 7.5: A schematic of the top view of the camera and flash or the high-speed camera and light sources

A mirror was mounted to the side of the die cavity. This allowed the recording device to “see” the front and the side of the jets at the same time. Rulers were glued along the bottom and sides of the die cavity to have a reference scale incorporated into the photographs. The placement of the flash turned out to be an important factor in obtaining clear pictures. It was found that the best placement of the flash was parallel to the mirror at the same distance from the layout as the camera (see Figure 7.5).

A high-speed, Red Lake Labs K20S4E 16mm film camera, outfitted with a 35mm Nikon lens, was used in this experiment. A powerful high-intensity light and two auxiliary

lights were focused on the test section to provide adequate lighting. The powerful light source was located behind the high-speed camera (the high-speed camera and the 35mm camera were positioned at the same angle from the test section). The two other light sources were positioned as shown in Figure 7.5. These two auxiliary lights were angled such that one faced directly into the mirror and the other one was positioned parallel to the mirror to detract the glare which would be "seen" by the camera.

Measurements of the time, velocity of the jet front, and jet widths were obtained from the high-speed photography. The velocity was calculated by utilizing the fact that there are 400 frames per second, or in other words, the difference between consecutive pictures is 0.0025 *sec*. The jet front height and width were determined directly from the 16mm film. The measured sizes were then converted to the real sizes. The vertical position of the jet front was determined by measuring the distance from the contact line to the bottom of the chamber for the "bulge" and the "spray" jets. For the jet with "fingers", the distance was measured from a specific hill or specific valley to the bottom of the cavity. The "bulge" jet is a jet with a smooth bulge while the "fingers" jet is a jet with hills and valleys on top of the bulge.

7.4 Experimental Procedure

The cylinder was filled from a water tank through a valve located in the lower front portion of the cylinder. The upper valve was used to release the air. A plexiglass cylinder was used to make certain that no air was present in the cylinder before injection. It was possible to eliminate almost all the air from the cylinder assembly. This allowed the injected water to be free from air during the time period that was studied.

The runner assembly was filled with water to the same level before each test run. The water level was at the height of the gate exit and was maintained by a tube which overflows the excess water. This tube was isolated from the system before the run by the

closure of a valve located at its connection to the main tube.

The hydraulic pump and controlling device were set to hold the cylinder in its retracted position before each run. The piston was then set into motion by triggering the wave generator through one cycle of the desired velocity function. Once the process was complete, the leftover water was sucked back into the cylinder and additional water was filled. The pressure in the cavity was measured prior to the injection. For the duration of the run the measuring port was cut off. A pressure lower than atmospheric was achieved by closing the top of the chamber and sucking off air with a ejector prior to the experiment. Some leaks in the system prevented pressures lower than $0.8atmosphere$.

7.5 Results and Discussion

The results of the experiments at atmospheric pressure are presented in Figures 7.6, 7.7, and 7.9 through 7.12. Figure 7.6 describes the width 1 of the bulge (see Figure 7.8 for description of width 1 and width 2) of the jet as a function of the time. Figure 7.6 describes the velocity of the jet front as a function of time for different runners. Figure 7.7 describes the growth rate of width 1 and width 2 for runner *A*. Figure 7.9 exhibits the velocity, V_e , of the jet front as a function of time for the three runners. Figure 7.10 describes the velocity for the runner *A* at three different pressure levels. Figures 7.11 and 7.12 illustrate two typical shapes of the jet at two different pressure levels.

The creation of a bulge at the jet front was found in all the runs at atmospheric pressure. The bulge created at the jet front grew in two directions perpendicular to the flow. Its widths are referred to herein as width 1 and width 2, and shown in Figure 7.8. These directions were away from the wall and along the side the wall. The bulge thickness grew roughly in a linear way with time. It was found that the growth rate of that thicknesses was smaller for higher jet velocity as is seen in Figure 7.6. For instance, the line for runner *A* which has a high jet velocity is the steepest. With the wide runner

Figure 7.6: The width of the bulge as a function of time for the three runners at atmospheric pressure

(runner *B*) the bulge reached its maximum possible width (the cover wall) before the total wall length was traversed.

Figure 7.7 describes the rate of growth of the bulge in the two directions for atmospheric pressure and runner *A*. The growth rate for the two widths decreases slightly with time. Width 1 did not reach its maximum in the length measured in the experiments, while width 2 reached its maximum. The initial rate of grow of width 2 was found to be larger than width 1. The difference between the widths growth is probably due to the wall effects.

The measurements of the jet occur during the accelerated period (0.01 to 0.02 *sec*) and, therefore, the differences among the velocity functions of the piston were not enough to create a considerable effect on the flow. The jet velocity was the only parameter that clearly affected the bulge growth. The jet velocity is different for the different gates.

One might suspect that the bulge is caused by gravitational force but the following

Figure 7.7: The growth rate of the width 1 and width 2 as a function of the time for atmospheric pressure and runner A

argument discards that. A water jet ejected in a vertically upward position is slowed down by gravity and reaches a fountain height h . Neglecting friction this height is described by the well known equation $h = \frac{V^2}{2}$. With an original velocity of 7.5m/s the height, h is 2.8m . The distance to the top of the runner assembly viewed in this study are less than 0.2m . Little deceleration can, therefore, have occurred by gravity in this range. Therefore, another mechanism must be responsible for the creation of the bulge. The air is displaced by the advancing jet which creates a pressure increase ($P_1 - P_2$) at the front and slows the jet (see Figure 7.8).

Figure 7.9 describes the velocity of the jet front at atmospheric pressure for the three runners. Figure 7.10 describes the velocity of the jet front at three different pressure levels. It has been observed before (Lefebvre 1989) that the front of a jet can become unstable and form “fingers”. This was observed here also. Figure 7.10 exhibits two measurements one of the hill and one of the valley of a finger at 1.2 atmosphere. The acceleration of

Figure 7.8: A schematic to explain the “bulge” growth

the jet front was found to change the sign during all the runs as shown in Figures 7.9 and 7.10. The author believes that this is not accidental and the velocity of the jet front accelerated and decelerated at different locations. This idea is also supported by the fact that the width velocity is following the same fluctuations. The velocity of hill of a finger (denoted in the Figure 7.10 by line *a*) is followed by the velocity of the valley line *b*, which describes the velocity of the valley.

The photos in Figures 7.11 and 7.12 show the jet structure for two pressure levels in the die cavity (1.0 and 0.8 atmosphere, respectively). The experiment at 0.8 atmosphere was planned to verify the conclusion that the bulge formation is not primarily caused by gravity. The photo in Figure 7.12 was a surprise to investigator. It shows a structure completely different from that in Figure 7.11. No explanation can be offered for this.

Figure 7.9: The velocity, V_e of the jet front as a function of time

7.6 Summary

A liquid jet injected into a chamber containing a gas forms at its front a bulge. It is believed that this deformation is primarily caused by the inertia of the surrounding gas which is being displaced by the advancing jet. Photos obtained with a high speed camera were evaluated to obtain quantitative information on the growth of the bulge and its deformation.

Figure 7.10: The velocity of the jet front as a function of the time

Figure 7.11: A water jet flows into a cavity with atmospheric pressure from down up. A mirror placed on the left side shows the other dimension. The bulge can be observed on the front of the jet from the two directions. The jet surface is relatively smooth.

Figure 7.12: The water jet flows into the cavity with vacuum pressure (~ -0.2 atmosphere). Flow starts as a spray and it is a spray all the way from the gate to the front of the jet.

Figure 7.13: The experimental apparatus with the author

Chapter 8

FINAL REMARKS

8.1 Introduction

In this Chapter, a summary of the major conclusions drawn from this work is presented. In these models several assumptions were made explicitly and implicitly. These assumptions are discussed and some ideas for future work are suggested.

8.2 Conclusions

- (i) There are critical vent/gate areas below which the ventilation is poor and above which the resistance to the air flow is minimal.
- (ii) The critical vent area in the vacuum venting and atmospheric venting is determined by two effects, the solidification process and the fluid mechanics of the gas flow. The solidification process is expressed by the filling time. Using these models, the vent area can be calculated relatively easily using the procedure outlined in Section 3.4 on page 23 and Section 4.4 on page 38.
- (iii) The critical gate area is controlled by similar effects as the vent area. The critical gate area is a function of the shot sleeve volume and the resistance in the runner.
- (iv) The success of the Pore Free Technique is controlled by the ratio of two effects: the mass transfer resistance to the reaction rate. The resistance to the mass transfer

can be controlled by modifying the design and operation parameters.

- (v) Equation (3.3) is based on an isentropic relationship. If any of the assumptions on which these models were constructed is not valid, then the flow inside the cylinder is not isentropic. However, in the case where the pressure in the cylinder remains constant the air/gas mass flow rate, $\dot{m}_{in}$, also remains constant during the filling process. This exists for any relationship between the pressure and temperature, whether the flow in the duct is adiabatic or not.
- (vi) The flow patterns of the jet entering into a die cavity can be classified as continuous wall sheet and spray flow. The continuous flow can be subclassified as “mushroom flow” and as a straight flow with a finger instability.
- (vii) The flow pattern of the jet is unstable and for the “same” conditions a different pattern can appear in a different run.

8.3 Recommendations for Future Research

The limitations of the present work and the recommendations for a future work are discussed here.

- (1) For simplification purposes, f , as it is expressed by $\frac{4fL}{D}$, was assumed to be constant. f varies with the Reynolds number especially when there is a transition in the flow regime. The gas flow rate is not constant, thus, the Reynolds number also varies. These variations might be significant for a compressible flow where the resistance due to geometrical changes is a function of the Reynolds number and the Mach number. This restriction can be analytically investigated.
- (2) The volumes of the vent and the runner were assumed for the models presented in Chapters 3-5 to be insignificant. Vent and runner designs sometimes have volumes

which cannot be neglected. These volumes can have two effects; they can increase the characteristic response time of the duct to pressure changes, or the flow itself can be changed. Looking into these volumes can clarify when these volumes affect the flow rate.

- (3) Whether or not the die has to be sealed when vacuum is applied is a practical question for die casters. The model presented in Chapter 3 can be expanded to include the sealing. The importance of the sealing has to be explained.
- (4) In the Pore Free Technique model, it was assumed that flows into and out of the cavity are negligible during the injection. The model can be extended to include these flows in and out, as well.
- (5) An accelerated velocity function during the piston stroke has been proposed to suppress the wave formation in the shot sleeve. The ramification of various piston velocity functions on the vent and gate area has to be studied.
- (6) These models (Chapters 3 and 5) have been verified in some cases in industry. However, experimental work to check the validity of the models in all conditions is advisable.
- (7) The experimental work has revealed that the jet entering a die cavity has two distinct flow patterns. Additional work has to be done for constructing an analytical model for these experimental results.
- (8) No-reaction of oxygen with liquid metal was assumed in the first three models (Chapters 3-5), but some reaction of the oxygen with liquid metal occurs. It creates second order effects which can be magnified when combined with the pressure variations. This combination should be examined.

Appendix A

Vacuum Tank Volume Calculations

A.1 The Model

In the construction of the model for vacuum venting (see Chapter 3), the vacuum-tank/cylinder pressure ratio was assumed to be less than the critical value. This critical value is a function of the resistance in the vent system, $\frac{4fL}{D}$. This restriction on the vacuum tank pressure means that the vacuum tank volume has to have a minimum value, which is a function of the system.

The conservations laws are used to obtain the ratio between the die volume to the vacuum tank volume. In order to continue with the calculations several assumptions have been made:

- (i) the air behavior can be modeled as an ideal gas,
- (ii) the heat transfer into and from the vacuum tank during the injection period is negligible,
- (iii) the air temperature in the vacuum tank before the injection is approximately at room temperature i.e. about 300K,
- (iv) the temperature drop across the venting ducts is in the range of 20%, of which as

much as 17% (see Figure 6.4 in Shapiro (1953)) can come as a result of friction which is included in the Fanno flow analysis, and,

(v) the air leakage into the tank and the die cavity can be neglected.

Figure A.1: A schematic of the air volumes before and after the injection

The conservation of air mass as shown in Figure A.1 (before the injection and after the injection) can be written

$$m_{total} = m_{cylinder} + m_{tank}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where m_{total} is the total mass in the cylinder (unfilled shot sleeve, runner and die cavity) and vacuum tank. Equation A.1 states that the air mass before the injection is equal to air mass after the injection.

The maximum pressure, P_{max} , in the vacuum tank is a function of $\frac{4fL}{D}$. In case that $\frac{4fL}{D} = 7$ the maximum pressure, P_{max} , in vacuum tank can be 25% of the atmospheric pressure (this pressure is after the injection). For higher values of $\frac{4fL}{D}$ the pressure has to be lower than that. $\frac{4fL}{D} = 7$ is a typical value of the resistance to the flow. The maximum mass occurs when the temperature is the lowest (the temperature in the vacuum tank is 0.8 atmosphere after the injection). In the termination of the filling process, the total mass in the vacuum tank is bounded by

$$m_{total} = \frac{f \left[\frac{4fL}{D} \right] V_{tank} P_{atm}}{0.8RT_{room}}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The air mass in the cylinder (unfilled shot sleeve, runner and die cavity) before the injection can be estimated as

$$m_{cylinder} = \frac{V(0)P_{atm}}{RT_{room}}. \quad (A.3)$$

The air mass in the vacuum tank before the injection is

$$m_{tank} = \frac{V_{tank}P_{vacuum}}{RT_{room}}. \quad (A.4)$$

P_{vacuum} is typically 25 inches mercury which is about $0.167 P_{atm}$. Combining equation (A.1), (A.2), (A.3) and (A.4) yields

$$\frac{f \left[\frac{4fL}{D} \right] V_{tank} P_{atm}}{0.8RT_{room}} = \frac{V(0)P_{atm}}{RT_{room}} + \frac{0.167V_{tank}P_{atm}}{RT_{room}}. \quad (A.5)$$

The solution for equation (A.5) for various $\frac{4fL}{D}$ is presented in Figure A.2.

Figure A.2: The volume ratio as a function of $\frac{4fL}{D}$

A.2 Summary

A procedure to calculate the minimum vacuum tank volume is presented. The vacuum tank volume is a function of the volume needed to be evacuated and the resistance in the vacuum venting system.

Appendix B

The Isentropic Relationship

B.1 Introduction

There are several possibilities to prove that the isentropic relationship is valid under the assumptions which these four models are constructed. One way is to look at a control volume moving with the piston at constant velocity (it is assumed that the piston velocity is constant). The conservation laws are used to demonstrate this relationship. There are three possibilities: one the pressure decreases which means that the air flows out of the control volume, two, the pressure increases and air flows into the control volume, three the trivial case, the pressure remains the same and no air flows into the control volume. The proof is carried out for all the cases.

B.2 Proof of the relationship

The assumptions which the proof was constructed for:

- (i) the gas in the cylinder is an ideal gas,
- (ii) there are no gradients in the temperature or pressure in the control volume, and
- (iii) the mixing processes are ideal.

Figure B.1: A schematic of an control volume moving with the piston at constant velocity

The mass balance on the control volume yields (see Figure B.1)

$$\frac{dm_{cv}}{dt} = -\dot{m}_{out} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where:

m_{cv} air mass at the control volume.

When m_{out} is negative the air flows into the system. Applying the first law to the control volume and combining equation (B.1) yield

$$\frac{d(m_{cv}e_{cv})}{dt} = -m_{out}h_{out} = \frac{dm_{cv}}{dt}h_{out}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Rearranging the right hand side of equation (B.2) yields

$$\frac{d(m_{cv}e_{cv})}{dt} = \frac{d(m_{cv}h_{out})}{dt} - m_{cv} \frac{dh_{out}}{dt}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Substituting the assumption of ideal gas into equation (B.3) yields

$$C_v \frac{d(m_{cv}T)}{dt} = C_p \left(\frac{d(m_{cv}T)}{dt} - m_{cv} \frac{dT}{dt} \right). \quad (\text{B.4})$$

A simplified form of equation (B.4) obtains the form

$$(C_p - C_v) \frac{d(m_{cv}T)}{dt} = C_p m_{cv} \frac{dT}{dt}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Rearranging equation (B.5) and canceling dt (since it is always positive and has non zero value) yields

$$\frac{C_p - C_v}{C_p} \frac{d(m_{cv}T)}{m_{cv}T} = \frac{dT}{T} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Integration of equation (B.6) yields

$$\left[\frac{T m_{cv2}}{T m_{cv1}} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} = \frac{T_2}{T_1} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Since the control volume is fixed in time equation (B.7) obtains the form

$$\left[\frac{P_2}{P_1} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} = \frac{T_2}{T_1} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

B.3 Conclusion and Comment

The isentropic relationship was proven to hold under the assumptions which the models in this work were constructed. This result should be expected since no gradients existed. Even when the isentropic relationship does not exist, k changes its value depending on the deviation from the isentropic relationship.

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